

PREPSOIL DELIVERABLE

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Authors:	Dr. Karel Charvat (LESP), Dr. Jaroslav Smejkal (LESP), Ing. Zbynek Krivanek (LESP)
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Contributors

Name	Organisation & Country
Karel Charvat	LESP, Czech Republic
Karel Charvat Jr.	LESP, Czech Republic
Jaroslav Smejkal	LESP, Czech Republic
Hanneke Heesmans	WR, Netherlands
Pierre Renault	INRAE, France
Gerald Jan Ellen	DELTA RES, Netherlands
Nora Szigeti	ÖMKi, Hungary
Judit Berenyi Uveges	ÖMKi, Hungary
Grzegorz Siebielec	IUNG, Poland
Jorge Federico Miranda Vélez	Aarhus University, Denmark
Margherita Caggiano	RE-SOIL FOUNDATION, Italy
Ivan Sanchez	CSIC, Spain
Mayte Gallego	ERIAFF, Spain

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List of Figures

- Figure 1 Soil health data generated by the citizen science projects (from Mason 2024)
- Figure 2 The tasks of citizen scientists, project coordinators and scientists in the citizen science projects (From Mason 2024)
- Figure 3 The tasks of citizen scientists, project coordinators and scientists in the citizen science projects
- Figure 4 Distribution of Citizen Science (CS) initiatives among partners
- Figure 5 Distribution of Citizen Science (CS) initiatives geographically
- Figure 6 Graph with type and main goal of the Citizen Science initiative
- Figure 7 Graph with scale of Citizen Science initiatives
- Figure 8 Graph with focus on Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients and salts
- Figure 9 Graph with focus on Soil organics carbon
- Figure 10 Graph with focus on landscape heterogeneity
- Figure 11 Graph with focus on Soil structure
- Figure 12 Graph with focus on Area of forest and other wooded lands
- Figure 13 Graph with focus on Vegetation cover

List of Tables

- Table 1 Focus areas of the Citizen Science initiatives
- Table 2 Involvement of various actor groups in the Citizen Science initiatives
- Table 3 Scale of community involvement in initiatives
- Table 4 Table summarizing the observed frequency of each strategy
- Table 5 Respondents' ages
- Table 6 Respondents' professional background
- Table 7 Respondents' Living Labs organisations
- Table 8 Respondents' country distribution
- Table 9 Respondents' previous participation in Citizen Science projects
- Table 10 Respondents' project experience
- Table 11 Respondents' satisfaction with existing methods of soil monitoring

Table of content

1. Introduction.....	7
1.1 What is Citizen Science.....	7
1.2 History of Citizen Science	8
1.3 European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) [17]	8
1.4 10 principles of Citizen Science	9
1.5 Methods of citizens' science	9
1.6 Citizen Science and Standardization	10
1.7 Examples of popular global initiatives	11
2. Soil Monitoring and Citizen Science Literature Review	11
2.1 Main Findings from Reviewed Literature.....	12
2.2 Usage of existing initiatives.....	14
3. EU projects focused on Citizen Science for Soil and Land Use Mapping	15
4. Existing Citizen Science Apps.....	16
5. Analysis of Citizens Science Initiatives collected by Prepsoil partners	17
5.1. Quantitative analysis.....	19
5.2. Qualitative analysis	29
6. Questionnaire analysis, workshops.....	30
7. Input for recommendation.....	33
7.1 D2.1 Synthesizing soil needs and drivers of change across Europe and land use types.....	34
7.2 D5.1 Analysis of knowledge base available to monitor soil indicators proposed under the Soil Mission.....	35
7.3 D5.2 Technical feasibility in using CLMS satellite-based EO to estimate soil health indicators	35
8. Analysis how Citizen Science can support needs and gaps.....	36
8.1 D2.1 Synthesizing soil needs and drivers of change across Europe and land use types.....	37
8.2 D5.1 Analysis of knowledge base available to monitor soil indicators proposed under the Soil Mission.....	38
8.3 D5.2 Technical feasibility in using CLMS satellite-based EO to estimate soil health indicators	39
9. Recommendations	39

**HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-01-01 /
Preparing the ground for healthy soils:
Building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge
PREPSOIL – 2022-2025**

9.1 Recommendations for Enhancing Soil Monitoring through Citizen Science.....	39
9.2 Recommendation for opened and standardization FAIR principles for Citizen Science.....	41
9.3. Data quality and validation	42
9.4 Ethics and privacy protection.....	43
10. Conclusion	44
Annex 1	
Annex 2	

Executive Summary

Citizen science refers to the involvement of non-specialist volunteers in scientific research activities, typically under the direction of professional scientists. This methodology facilitates extensive data collection and analysis across various scientific fields. It leverages collective public effort, often utilizing digital platforms to gather and analyze large datasets, which enhances the scope and accessibility of scientific research. This participatory approach also contributes to the dissemination of scientific knowledge and the improvement of public scientific literacy [1].

The "Prepsoil" deliverable D5.3. provides an in-depth exploration of the role of Citizen Science in enhancing environmental and soil health monitoring. The document begins by defining Citizen Science and tracing its historical roots from ancient practices to its current role in modern scientific inquiry. It highlights the evolution of Citizen Science into a vital component of scientific research that not only increases data accuracy but also enhances public involvement in scientific endeavors across various domains.

The literature review in the document emphasizes how Citizen Science has been integrated into soil monitoring, detailing the methodologies, outcomes, and challenges encountered. It underscores the pivotal role that Citizen Science plays in broadening the scope and enhancing the precision of environmental monitoring, thereby contributing significantly to sustainable agricultural practices and urban planning.

The document also discusses various EU projects that exemplify the integration of Citizen Science into soil and land use monitoring, showcasing diverse methodologies and outcomes aimed at sustainable natural resource management. It highlights the innovative use of mobile applications in Citizen Science, which enable public participation and contribute to scientific research and data accuracy.

A detailed analysis of Citizen Science initiatives collected by Prepsoil partners is provided, offering insights into the trends, challenges, and successes of these initiatives. This includes both quantitative and qualitative evaluations that reveal how these projects have been implemented across various European regions.

Feedback from a questionnaire distributed during workshops with various Living Labs further enriches the understanding of current practices and challenges in soil monitoring. This feedback underscores the diversity of participant involvement and highlights areas for improvement in monitoring methodologies.

Drawing from these comprehensive analyses, the document proposes detailed recommendations to optimize the integration of Citizen Science into soil health monitoring. These recommendations focus on enhancing soil monitoring through the expansion of data coverage using public participation and the standardization of methodologies across different regions. The adoption of advanced technologies such as remote sensing and AI is encouraged to improve monitoring accuracy.

The recommendations emphasize the importance of promoting openness and standardization in line with FAIR principles—making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Strengthening collaborations between organizations like the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) is highlighted as essential for promoting the use of open standards, which improve data interoperability and integration into broader scientific and policy frameworks.

The recommendations emphasize the necessity for robust data validation mechanisms to improve the quality and reliability of data collected through citizen science. This involves deploying comprehensive training programs and incorporating advanced technologies to support and verify data gathered by citizen scientists. It might be beneficial to consider the implications of using AI in such settings, ensuring a balanced approach that addresses both the benefits and potential limitations.

Lastly, ethical practices and privacy protection are stressed as increasingly important, especially with the integration of new AI technologies. Establishing comprehensive ethical frameworks, ensuring informed consent, and maintaining transparency about AI algorithms are crucial steps to navigate the ethical and privacy challenges presented by modern technologies.

Overall, the document encapsulates a strategic vision for integrating Citizen Science into environmental monitoring and management, providing a roadmap for enhancing scientific research and public engagement through collaborative and inclusive approaches.

1. Introduction

1.1 What is Citizen Science

Citizen science is a participatory form of scientific research that engages non-professional volunteers in various stages of the scientific process. This collaborative approach involves the public in identifying research questions, conducting investigations, collecting and analyzing data, and even developing technologies. The definition of citizen science, according to Mäkipää (2020) [2], emphasizes its collaborative nature, where the general public participates actively in the production of scientific knowledge.

The scope of citizen science has expanded significantly, particularly in fields like biological and environmental sciences, where it has been utilized to enhance data accuracy and increase public participation in scientific endeavors (Suomela, 2012) [3]. Houllier (2017) [4] broadens this definition to include any deliberate participation by non-scientists in scientific research, ranging from short-term data collection efforts to more sustained involvement.

The impact of citizen science has been substantial, contributing to high citation metrics in specific scientific domains, such as space science and biodiversity (Odenwald, 2018) [5]; (Bedessem, 2021) [6]. It has also been a tool for addressing real-world problems and enhancing educational outcomes in science and environmental awareness (Mercer, 2018) [7]. Despite its many benefits, citizen science faces challenges such as ensuring data quality and managing the limitations associated with public involvement, which often focuses on more accessible areas, potentially overlooking other critical ecosystems (Cooper, 2014) [8]. However, strategies have been developed to improve data reliability and the overall effectiveness of citizen science projects (Fritz, 2018) [9].

Citizen science is defined as the engagement of volunteers in scientific research to collaboratively generate and use data in various scientific fields. This definition is supported by multiple sources, including the Citizen Science Association [10] and platforms like SciStarter [11] and Zooniverse [12], which highlight the educational and collaborative aspects of citizen science, contributing to both scientific research and community engagement. Moreover, providing feedback to participants about the outcomes and impacts of their contributions is crucial. Encouraging citizen scientists to participate in the publication and presentation of results can further enhance the value and educational aspect of their involvement, making the scientific process more inclusive and transparent.

1.2 History of Citizen Science

As detailed in the publication by Havens (2013) [13], citizen science involves the public in scientific research across various disciplines. This participatory approach is not a modern innovation but has deep historical roots, showcasing a long-standing tradition of public participation in science, from ancient observations to more formalized projects in the recent centuries. The genesis of citizen science can be traced back to ancient civilizations. Notably, the earliest known phenological records were made by the Chinese around 974 BCE, meticulously documenting natural events. This practice was echoed in Japan by the 9th century CE with systematic records of cherry blossom timings, a tradition that is celebrated even today. In the 18th century, Robert Marsham, a British landowner, initiated systematic phenological recordings, a practice that his family upheld until 1958. These early efforts established a foundation for phenological studies, which are crucial in environmental and climate sciences today. The 20th century marked significant milestones in the formalization of citizen science. In 1900, the Audubon Society initiated the Christmas Bird Count in the United States, pioneering organized citizen science projects aimed at collecting ecological data on a large scale. By 1911, the U.S. National Weather Service began incorporating observations from amateur meteorologists, integrating citizen-contributed data into national scientific operations. The official recognition of this field within the academic community came with the coining of the term "citizen science" in 1996 by researchers at the Cornell Laboratory of Ornithology. In different linguistic and cultural contexts, the term and approach can vary. For instance, in French, the term 'recherche participative' is used, which translates to 'participatory research.' This concept often extends beyond traditional citizen science frameworks to include collaborations that may only involve scientists and specific stakeholders, such as in Living Labs (LL). Additionally, the use of serious games in research, particularly in social and humanities sciences, illustrates another dimension of participatory research where the interaction between players generates data or insights valuable for scientific inquiry. This broader interpretation underlines the adaptability and expansive potential of participatory research methodologies in varying academic and cultural contexts [14]. The late 20th and early 21st centuries saw a transformation in citizen science through the advent of the internet and digital technologies. Projects like Galaxy Zoo [15], launched in 2007, leveraged the internet to engage volunteers worldwide in classifying galaxies. That same year, Project BudBurst [16] gathered phenological data across the United States, showcasing the adaptability of citizen science to modern technological tools. By 2013, the landscape of citizen science had expanded significantly to include hundreds of projects worldwide, engaging millions of participants and covering a vast array of scientific disciplines.

The historical trajectory of citizen science from informal, localized observations to a globally recognized and vital component of scientific research underscores its enduring value. This evolution highlights the potential of citizen science to contribute to diverse scientific fields and address complex global challenges, fostering a broad and inclusive engagement with science. Through projects like these, citizen science has proven to be an effective tool for data collection, education, and public engagement in science.

1.3 European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) [17]

The European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) promotes democratizing science by advancing citizen science across Europe and enhancing public involvement in research. ECSA acts as a central hub for citizen science initiatives, aiming to build a strong community, provide quality tools and training, and establish good practice standards. It advocates for the integration of citizen-generated data in decision-making and supports technological advancements in research. ECSA organizes

several working groups that focus on various aspects such as the sustainable management of urban green spaces, agricultural practices in food systems, and standardizing citizen science data and metadata in collaboration with entities like the Open Geospatial Consortium. Through policy engagement, ECSA integrates citizen science into environmental and educational frameworks, influencing policies on climate change and natural resource management. This association plays a vital role in promoting scientific literacy, fostering community engagement, and ensuring that citizen science contributes significantly to addressing societal and scientific challenges.

1.4 10 principles of Citizen Science

The "10 Principles of Citizen Science" were developed by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and introduced by the "Sharing best practice and building capacity" working group, led by the Natural History Museum London. First presented at the ECSA General Assembly in 2015, these principles have been broadly embraced by the global citizen science community.

Overview of the 10 Principles:

1. **Active Participation:** Citizen science projects involve citizens actively, particularly in data collection, analysis, and dissemination.
2. **Scientific Methodology:** Projects are designed to generate reliable, high-quality data and often contribute to scientific research.
3. **Mutual Benefit:** Participants gain learning and community benefits, while scientists gain valuable data.
4. **Contribution to Common Goals:** Projects contribute to scientific research and community interests.
5. **Open and Transparent:** Methods and data are transparent and shared openly where possible.
6. **Accessible Data:** Data and metadata are accessible to all, ensuring that the data can be reused effectively.
7. **Feedback:** Participants receive feedback on how their input is used and what the research findings are.
8. **Ethical Considerations:** Projects address ethical and legal implications of the research and the welfare of participants and the environment.
9. **Learning Opportunities:** Projects provide educational opportunities that enhance scientific literacy and research skills.
10. **Sustainability and Flexibility:** Projects are designed to be sustainable and flexible to adapt to changing conditions and feedback.

These principles serve as a framework to foster excellence across all aspects of citizen science, ensuring that projects adhere to standards that promote valid scientific outcomes and engage communities effectively. They have been translated into multiple languages and are utilized globally, underlining their universal applicability and relevance.

1.5 Methods of citizens' science

Citizen science (CS) methodologies can be broadly classified across several dimensions [18], reflecting the diversity of approaches used in these participatory research projects. One way to classify citizen science projects is by the level of contribution required from participants [19]. This includes crowdsourcing, where the public contributes data or solves simple problems with minimal training; distributed intelligence, which requires participants to process or analyze information needing specific skills; participatory monitoring, involving systematic data collection and analysis

often using personal or local knowledge; and co-creation, where projects are collaboratively designed and executed by both scientists and participants from the very beginning [20].

In terms of the type of activity, citizen science methods vary widely. Data collection involves participants gathering information through observations or measurements, while data processing might see them analyzing or categorizing data, often online. Data interpretation engages volunteers in deriving conclusions or identifying patterns from the data, and problem solving involves tackling specific scientific or community challenges through innovative approaches [21].

The design of citizen science projects also varies. Contributory projects are predominantly designed by scientists with participants mainly involved in data collection. Collaborative projects allow for shared responsibilities in both the design and interpretation phases. Co-created projects, on the other hand, are fully integrated, with participants having equal input in all stages from problem definition to the publication of findings.

Another classification criterion is the field of application. Projects may focus on ecological and environmental monitoring, recording data related to natural environments or wildlife. Urban science projects study city living aspects like pollution or infrastructure, while social science projects gather data on human behaviors or societal issues. Astronomy and space science projects engage the public in tasks like observing celestial events or classifying galaxies.

Finally, the utilization of technology is a crucial classification factor in citizen science projects. Some projects operate entirely online, using websites or apps to collect or analyze both quantitative data, such as numerical measurements, and qualitative data, such as observations or descriptive records. Meanwhile, other projects require physical presence in specific locations or environments, termed on-site projects, which may involve gathering data through direct sensory observations or structured interviews. Hybrid projects combine both online and on-site elements, providing a versatile approach to data collection. This integration allows for a broader range of data types and enhances participant engagement by accommodating different methods of interaction and data reporting.

These classifications help to categorize the vast array of citizen science projects, providing clarity on the structure and goals of each initiative, ensuring participants can align their interests and capabilities with suitable projects.

1.6 Citizen Science and Standardization

Most current initiatives in citizen science are proprietary, which poses challenges in data sharing and interoperability. Nevertheless, initiatives like those led by the European Citizen Science Association (ESCA) in collaboration with the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) are making strides toward non-proprietary, standardized approaches. ESA, through its Citizen Science Domain Working Group, champions the use of OGC open standards to address key issues such as data quality, privacy, and security [22]. The OGC's efforts, particularly through the Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) and SensorThings API standards, are central to improving interoperability among different data systems. The Citizen Science Interoperability Experiment by OGC demonstrates how applying these standards can enhance data integration and interaction across various information models in citizen science projects.

Simultaneously, the DataBio project also leverages OGC's SWE standard, alongside the SensLog platform and HSLayers NG applications, to manage and visualize sensor data and Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) [23], [24]. This system employs a PostgreSQL database with PostGIS and adapts the ISO's Observations & Measurements conceptual model to fit the specific needs of citizen science, focusing on enhancing data interoperability and security. DataBio's adoption of Open Linked Data principles using the Virtuoso graph model engine, and its development of a

lightweight specification for Map Compositions using HTML5 and JSON, further contribute to the dynamic and interactive sharing of geographic information.

1.7 Examples of popular global initiatives

OpenStreetMap (OSM) serves as a prime example of citizen science through its crowd-sourced data collection model, where volunteers globally contribute to geographical data updates. Although not originally designed as a citizen science project, OSM has naturally evolved into one, embracing collaborative and open data practices. This model significantly enriches geographic knowledge by mapping diverse features such as roads, buildings, and points of interest. The involvement of citizens becomes particularly crucial in regions where research teams alone cannot cover all areas and where data from public administrations are not publicly available. Beyond its contribution to scientific databases, OSM's crowd-sourced data also supports critical applications such as disaster relief, urban planning, and navigation, underscoring the extensive utility and impact of its collaborative data collection approach [25].

Geocaching, primarily a recreational activity centered around a treasure-hunt experience, does not systematically collect scientific data and thus does not fit the traditional mold of a citizen science initiative. However, it indirectly contributes to citizen science through casual observations made by participants. Geocachers often explore remote or less frequented areas where they encounter unique natural features or wildlife. While there is no formal protocol for data collection, contributions such as environmental stewardship through initiatives like 'Cache In, Trash Out' help in promoting conservation efforts, aligning with broader citizen science goals [26].

Geo-Wiki is a direct citizen science platform launched in 2009, designed to improve the accuracy of global land cover maps. It utilizes gamification to engage users in classifying satellite and aerial imagery, contributing to environmental monitoring efforts. This platform allows for widespread participation in environmental data collection, focusing on land use, pollution, and other critical environmental or socioeconomic factors. Geo-Wiki exemplifies a structured approach to citizen science, leveraging global participation to enhance environmental databases and decision-making tools. In summary, while OSM and Geo-Wiki engage communities in scientific data collection and validation, contributing significantly to environmental research and management, Geocaching offers a more informal contribution to citizen science, primarily through its potential for incidental environmental observations and stewardship activities [27].

2. Soil Monitoring and Citizen Science Literature Review

In recent years, the application of citizen science has become a critical method in augmenting soil monitoring practices. This methodology involves the systematic utilization of non-professional individuals to collect, analyze, and report environmental data. This chapter conducts a detailed literature review on the role of citizen science in soil monitoring, presenting the methodologies, outcomes, and challenges as documented in various studies from Europe and other regions. The integration of citizen science with established scientific methods has broadened the scope and enhanced the precision of soil monitoring, providing methodological innovations to address challenges in environmental science. Studies by Kotovirta (2015) [28], Head (2020) [29], and Rossiter (2015) [30] have illustrated how citizen science contributes to the enhancement of soil data collection, the improvement of digital soil map accuracy, and the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices such as precision farming, organic agriculture, and regenerative agricultural techniques. These contributions are in alignment with global targets such as the Sustainable

Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 15 (Life on Land), which focuses on protecting, restoring, and promoting sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, and SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), which emphasizes sustainable agricultural practices as a means to end hunger, achieve food security, and improve nutrition. Furthermore, the literature review extends to examining the impact of citizen science on land use and cover monitoring in agricultural, forest, and urban settings. The inclusion of citizen science in these areas has been instrumental in providing extensive data that support more accurate land use classification and change detection, which are essential for planning and development purposes. This comprehensive analysis not only underscores the utility of citizen science in diverse environmental contexts but also delineates the practical challenges encountered, such as data validation, volunteer retention, and the integration of citizen-derived data with professional datasets.

2.1 Main Findings from Reviewed Literature

Main findings from the reviewed literature include enhanced data collection and coverage, as demonstrated by Kotovirta et al. (2015), who highlighted the utility of combining citizen science with Earth observation to augment data collection, particularly in forest biomass analysis and soil moisture validation. Head et al. (2020) discussed how citizen science platforms can effectively supplement structured soil monitoring programs, thus enhancing the data coverage necessary for comprehensive environmental assessments. Cost-effectiveness and community engagement are evident in initiatives like those proposed by Rossiter et al. (2015), which utilize digital soil mapping to not only foster community involvement but also reduce the costs associated with extensive soil surveys by leveraging local knowledge and resources. However, there are challenges in implementation, as noted by Loosa et al. (2015) [31] and Ebitu et al. (2021) [32], including maintaining volunteer motivation, ensuring data quality, and overcoming methodological constraints. Policy and decision-making support are enhanced through contributions from studies like those by Mason (2024) [33] and Hemment et al. (2017) [34], which show how citizen science projects can influence policy-making and support decision-making processes in agriculture and land management by providing real-time, reliable data.

Mason (2024) provided deep analysis of literature sources in the realm of soil monitoring, citizen science contributes significantly through targeted observations that align with key mission methods.

Figure 1 Soil health data generated by the citizen science projects (from Mason 2024)

Figure 2 The tasks of citizen scientists, project coordinators and scientists in the citizen science projects (From Mason 2024)

Figure 3 The tasks of citizen scientists, project coordinators and scientists in the citizen science projects

His reviews synthesize these findings to provide an in-depth understanding of citizen science's role in soil monitoring, exploring how it has been applied across diverse geographical and ecological

contexts. It discusses the successes of these initiatives, such as extensive data collection and enhanced community engagement, as well as the challenges they face, including potential biases from non-professional involvement, difficulties integrating citizen-collected data with traditional scientific datasets, and inconsistencies in data quality. To ensure broad and effective participation, strategies to access and engage citizens often include utilizing digital platforms for easy data entry and communication, conducting outreach through community workshops, and collaborating with local educational institutions and NGOs. These approaches help to lower barriers to participation, making it easier for people from varied backgrounds to contribute to scientific research. The review also suggests future directions for research and practical applications, emphasizing the need for improved methods to train volunteers and enhance data validation processes to overcome current limitations. Strategies to involve citizens effectively include implementing robust training programs, using engaging and user-friendly data collection technologies, and ensuring transparent communication about the impact of their contributions to enhance continued participation and data reliability. These strategies are crucial for integrating citizen science into traditional soil monitoring frameworks, which promise enhanced environmental stewardship and increased public involvement in scientific research.

2.2 Usage of existing initiatives

The utilization of existing citizen science initiatives, particularly OpenStreetMap (OSM) [35] , Geocaching [36] Geo-Wiki [37], and the Open Land Use Map [38], demonstrates a strategic approach to leveraging widespread public participation in environmental monitoring and management. These platforms provide foundational frameworks for integrating large-scale volunteer contributions with official datasets, enhancing the breadth and accuracy of environmental data collection. Citizens are often motivated to participate by a combination of factors including personal interest in environmental issues, community involvement, educational opportunities, and the intrinsic satisfaction of contributing to scientific and societal progress. These initiatives actively engage diverse groups, encompassing varying ages, genders, socio-economic backgrounds, and cultural contexts, thereby enriching the data with a wide range of perspectives and enhancing the overall robustness of environmental monitoring. Understanding the differences in motivation and participation among these diverse groups helps tailor approaches that maximize engagement and effectiveness, ensuring that citizen science remains an inclusive and empowering tool across all segments of society

OpenStreetMap (OSM) serves as a pivotal tool in the crowdsourcing landscape, providing a freely editable map of the world supported by a global community of mappers who contribute and maintain data about roads, trails, cafés, railway stations, and much more. This vast repository of geospatial data is invaluable for projects that require up-to-date maps and geographic information system (GIS) data, particularly useful in areas lacking official cartographic coverage or where rapid changes in land use or infrastructure occur (Haklay and Weber, 2008) [39].

Geocaching, another prominent citizen science initiative, involves a community-driven, location-based game where participants use GPS devices to hide and seek containers, called "geocaches," at specific locations marked by coordinates all over the globe. This activity not only engages individuals in outdoor recreational activities but also encourages participants to observe and report on environmental conditions, such as changes in vegetation cover or land use, at cache locations. This inadvertent collection of geospatial data provides a unique dataset that can be used for environmental monitoring and educational purposes (Abdo 2020) [40], (Kreta 2018) [40].

Geo-Wiki is a global network of volunteers who engage in the validation of land cover and land use data derived from remotely sensed images. It acts as a tool for improving the quality of global land cover maps, which are crucial for a variety of scientific and practical applications in areas such as climate action, agricultural monitoring, and urban planning. The platform allows users to contribute to the creation of a hybrid land cover map by validating existing data and contributing new observations (Fritz et al., 2012 [42]; See et al., 2015 [43]). By harnessing the power of crowdsourcing, Geo-Wiki facilitates more accurate ground truthing of land cover classifications, improving the reliability of environmental datasets used in large-scale ecological and geographical studies.

Additionally, the Open Land Use Map, initiated by Mildorf et al. (2014) [44], aims to create an improved worldwide land use map by integrating various datasets and volunteer efforts. This initiative not only extends the capabilities of existing mapping solutions but also enhances the accessibility of land use data, which is critical for analyzing environmental changes and supporting sustainable development.

The integration of these citizen-led initiatives with larger environmental monitoring programs offers significant advantages, including the diversification of data sources, increased spatial and temporal resolution of environmental observations, and enhanced community engagement in scientific research. However, potential limitations include the variability in data quality due to non-professional data collectors, the challenges of verifying the accuracy of the vast amounts of data generated, and the need for sustained volunteer motivation and participation. Moreover, the tangible impact of their contributions towards global sustainability goals serves as a powerful motivator for citizens, reinforcing their engagement and dedication to these projects by showcasing the direct benefits of their participation in environmental stewardship and policy shaping.

Literature analysis demonstrates that to effectively integrate these citizen science initiatives into larger frameworks, it is essential to develop clear protocols for data validation and implement robust training programs for participants. Additionally, providing feedback and demonstrating the impact of contributors' efforts can significantly enhance volunteer engagement and data quality. These strategies, supported by scholarly research, ensure that the integration of citizen science with professional environmental monitoring not only enriches the data quality but also fosters a more informed and involved public. These strategies ensure that the integration of citizen science with professional environmental monitoring not only enriches the data quality but also fosters a more informed and involved public.

3. EU projects focused on Citizen Science for Soil and Land Use Mapping

The European Union has been at the forefront of integrating citizen science into the monitoring of soil and land use, demonstrating a robust commitment to enhancing environmental stewardship through public engagement. Several projects exemplify this integration, showcasing diverse methodologies and outcomes aimed at sustainable natural resource management.

LUCAS (Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey) [45], [46] utilizes crowdsourcing to enhance land cover and land use data collection through mobile apps like FotoQuest Austria. Participants contribute by generating reference data and photographs, which are validated against authoritative LUCAS survey data, aiding in change detection. This approach not only enriches the

dataset but also fosters public involvement in scientific research. More information is available on the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) website [47].

CROPS [48] is an initiative started in February 2024 focusing on upscaling citizen science activities across Europe, developing standardized protocols for data collection, sharing, and accessibility. It addresses various areas including soil health and food security, promoting a systematic approach to citizen science. Details can be found on the IIASA website.

Soil Health Related Citizen-Science Projects [49], reviewed by EUSO in collaboration with ECHO, synthesize previous projects focused on soil health. This initiative creates a repository of resources from past efforts, identifying knowledge gaps and methods employed, thereby enhancing the continuity and efficacy of future projects. Additional information is available on the ECHO project website.

LandSense [50] engages citizens in collecting in-situ observations to support environmental monitoring systems. It extends existing initiatives like Geo-Wiki and FotoQuest, integrating satellite data with citizen science for comprehensive land cover monitoring. Further details can be accessed on the IIASA LandSense project page.

EU Soil and Land Initiatives outline a framework and concrete measures set by the European Commission to protect and restore soils, ensuring sustainable use through strategies like the EU soil strategy for 2030 and the proposed Soil Monitoring Law. More information can be accessed on the European Commission's environment page.

These projects collectively highlight the EU's strategy to incorporate citizen science into environmental monitoring and policy-making processes. Each project contributes uniquely to the broader goal of sustainable soil management and land use monitoring.

The potential limitations of these initiatives include challenges related to data accuracy, volunteer retention, and the integration of citizen-generated data with professional scientific analyses. To mitigate these issues, projects often implement comprehensive training for participants and develop advanced tools and mobile applications that facilitate data collection and validation. These tools include GPS locators, cameras for capturing soil profiles, and user-friendly forms for data entry, which are integral to the success of projects like **ECHO**. Additionally, creating open-access repositories ensures that the collected data are available to researchers, policymakers, and the public, enhancing transparency and usability.

In summary, the strategic engagement of citizens in soil and land use monitoring through these projects not only enhances the scope of environmental data collection but also empowers individuals—those members of the general public who participate as citizen scientists—to contribute meaningfully to scientific research and sustainable practices. Further information about these initiatives and their contributions to soil and land monitoring can be explored through their respective websites and publications.

4. Existing Citizen Science Apps

The landscape of mobile applications dedicated to citizen science is diverse, each targeting specific aspects of environmental and biodiversity data collection. **FotoQuest Go**, for instance, is a mobile application explicitly crafted for collecting ground-based land cover and land use data. Utilizing a protocol derived from the Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey (LUCAS), users complete “quests” by taking photographs at designated locations in four cardinal directions. This application integrates gamification, offering prizes and monetary rewards to enhance participant engagement. The accuracy of data collected by FotoQuest Go correlates well with professional data, particularly for major land cover types. It has also been adapted for other uses such as forest parameter collection

by the FAO and building information verification by the French National Mapping Agency. More details about FotoQuest Go can be found on the FotoQuest website, EU-Citizen.Science, and the IIASA website [51].

iNaturalist [52] is another prominent application, globally recognized for its role in biodiversity monitoring. This app, developed jointly by the California Academy of Sciences and the National Geographic Society, enables users to record and share wildlife observations, contributing significantly to global biodiversity databases.

Pl@ntNet [53] is specifically designed for plant identification and helps users recognize plant species from photographs. It is developed by a consortium that includes several French institutions, showcasing a robust approach to botany-oriented citizen science.

eBird [54] is a specialized birdwatching application that allows users to log bird sightings. Managed by the Cornell Lab of Ornithology, it contributes to avian biodiversity records and is extensively utilized not only in the USA but across Europe as well.

Citizen Science Central offers a broader platform that encompasses a variety of projects ranging from environmental monitoring to biodiversity. Supported by the EU-Citizen Science platform, it serves as a hub for numerous citizen science initiatives across Europe.

Marine Debris Tracker, focused on marine conservation, is designed to track and map marine litter. This app represents a collaborative effort between the NOAA and the University of Georgia, highlighting the importance of tackling marine pollution through citizen engagement.

Project Noah provides an educational platform that encourages the public to learn about wildlife while contributing to scientific research by submitting wildlife observations. These observations are cataloged and can be accessed by scientists to study biodiversity, track species distributions, and monitor changes in wildlife populations over time. It operates globally and has a substantial user base in Europe, emphasizing its international appeal and educational value.

Each of these applications plays a critical role in enhancing scientific research through public participation, demonstrating the potential of mobile technology in facilitating widespread citizen involvement in scientific endeavors.

During the PrepSoil project, a new mobile app was developed and tested to facilitate soil and land use monitoring. This app serves as a digital tool that enables citizens to easily access soil-related information and contribute real-time soil observations. The PREPSOIL Mobile App provides functionalities like creating soil quests, which are critical for gathering localized environmental data directly from citizens. This initiative not only extends the capabilities of existing citizen science tools but also enhances the accessibility and accuracy of land use data, which is essential for analyzing environmental changes and supporting sustainable development practices. The development and testing phase included involvement from selected Living Labs and initiatives, ensuring the app met practical field requirements and user expectations.

5. Analysis of Citizens Science Initiatives collected by Prepsoil partners

In 2023, partners of the Prepsoil project undertook the task of compiling a comprehensive database of citizen science initiatives, focusing predominantly on activities within their respective countries. This collected data, which forms a significant part of the annex to this report, provides a foundational resource for understanding the scope and impact of citizen science across various regions. This chapter delves into both quantitative and qualitative analyses of the initiatives

documented in the database. Through this dual approach, we aim to present a thorough evaluation of the trends, challenges, and successes characterizing these citizen science endeavors, offering insights that could inform future strategies and collaborations in the field. We collected all together information about 96 initiatives, which is comparable with studies from literature. The initiatives were collected by 11 partners. The questionnaire used for analyzing Citizen Science (CS) initiatives in the context of the PREPSOIL project appears to have a comprehensive structure designed to gather detailed information about various aspects of these initiatives. Here's a breakdown of its structure based on the provided header:

1. PREPSOIL Partner: The organization or partner responsible for the initiative.
2. Name of Initiative: The title or name of the citizen science initiative.
3. Type and Main Goal of the CS Initiative: The nature (e.g., research, education, community engagement) and primary objectives of the initiative.
4. Is Initiative Active: Indicates whether the initiative is currently ongoing.
5. Country/Location: Geographic location where the initiative is based or active.
6. Scale: The scope or reach of the initiative (e.g., local, regional, national, international).
7. Focus Areas: This includes multiple columns each dedicated to a specific environmental or soil-related focus area:
 - Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients and salts
 - Soil organic carbon
 - Soil structure (including bulk density and the absence of soil sealing and erosion)
 - Soil biodiversity
 - Soil nutrients and pH
 - Vegetation cover
 - Landscape heterogeneity
 - Area of forest and other wooded lands
8. Actor Groups: The different groups involved or targeted by the initiative (e.g., scientists, local communities, policymakers).
9. Data Collection Description: A text description of what data are collected.
10. Community Size: Size of the community involved or impacted by the initiative.
11. Strategy to Reach Stakeholders: Describes the methods used to engage or involve stakeholders in the initiative.
12. Open Access to Data/Licensing: Information on the accessibility of the data collected and any licensing terms.
13. Ethical Limitations: Any ethical concerns or limitations associated with the initiative.
14. Used Standards: Standards followed in the data collection or project execution.
15. Validation Procedure: How the data or results are validated within the framework of the initiative.
16. URL: A link to the website or online resource where more information about the initiative can be found.

This structure is designed to ensure a holistic understanding of each citizen science initiative, from logistical details like location and activity status to more nuanced information about data handling, ethical considerations, and stakeholder engagement strategies. It allows the PREPSOIL project to assess and compare different initiatives effectively, facilitating insights into best practices and areas for improvement in citizen science as it relates to soil and environmental monitoring.

5.1. Quantitative analysis

In reviewing the distribution of Citizen Science (CS) initiatives (see an Annex 1) as documented in the provided dataset, we observe the following:

- INRAE France leads with 16 initiatives, followed by DELTARES with 12, and ZALF with 11. Aarhus University has contributed to 8 initiatives, while IUNG is associated with 6. Both Wageningen Research and LESPROJEKT have each launched 5 initiatives. ERIAFF (FUNDECYT), OMKI, and RE-SOIL FOUNDATION have each managed 4 initiatives, and CSIC has undertaken 1 initiative.

Figure 4 Distribution of Citizen Science (CS) initiatives among partners

- Geographically, France is the most frequently covered country with 16 initiatives. The Netherlands and Denmark are also prominently featured with 8 and 7 initiatives respectively, matched by Germany's 7. Poland and the Czech Republic each have 5 initiatives. Hungary is involved in 3 initiatives, while Spain is associated with a total of 4, considering various specific locations within the country. Additionally, there are initiatives that span multiple countries, with two initiatives covering 50 countries each.

Figure 5 Distribution of Citizen Science (CS) initiatives geographically

- The dataset categorizes Citizen Science (CS) initiatives into several types based on their main goals and methods, revealing a diverse array of approaches. The most common type is "Participatory science," with 31 initiatives, demonstrating a strong emphasis on active engagement and collaboration between scientists and citizens. "Crowdsourcing" follows with 14 initiatives, focusing on collecting data from a broad base of participants. "Distributed intelligence" includes 7 initiatives, which involve distributed problem-solving and data processing among numerous volunteers. Additionally, there are 4 initiatives categorized under "Extreme citizens science," and 3 initiatives described as "Serious game," which are designed to engage participants in scientific inquiry through gamification.

Figure 6 Graph with type and main goal of the Citizen Science initiative

- In terms of their operational status, the majority of initiatives, totaling 59, are currently active. Conversely, 16 initiatives are inactive, with 16 marked as "not active". There is also one initiative where the activity status is unclear, noted as "not known."
- The scale of Citizen Science (CS) initiatives in the dataset ranges from local to international, with varying degrees of participation across geographical boundaries: National scale initiatives are most prevalent, with a total of 35. This demonstrates a strong focus on engaging citizens within individual countries. European scale initiatives total 11. Regional scale initiatives appear 12 times. Local initiatives are noted 10 times. This data highlights a strong tendency for CS initiatives to operate within national contexts, though there is significant representation at European and regional levels, illustrating a broad reach and diversity in the scope of these scientific endeavors.

Figure 7 Graph with scale of Citizen Science initiatives

- In the dataset, the focus areas of the Citizen Science (CS) initiatives pertaining to soil and environmental parameters are as follows: 21 initiatives focus on the presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients, and salts, 16 initiatives are dedicated to studying soil organic carbon, 17 initiatives concentrate on soil structure, including bulk density and the absence of soil sealing and erosion. 32 initiatives emphasize soil biodiversity, making it the most prevalent focus area among the listed parameters. 21 initiatives address soil nutrients and pH. 23 initiatives are involved in examining vegetation cover, 9 initiatives explore landscape heterogeneity, 10 initiatives focus on the area of forest and other wooded lands. These statistics indicate a robust engagement across a variety of soil and environmental research themes within the CS initiatives, with a particularly strong emphasis on soil biodiversity

Table 1 Focus areas of the Citizen Science initiatives

Focus Area	Number of Initiatives
Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients, and salts	21
Soil organic carbon	16
Soil structure (including bulk density, absence of soil sealing and erosion)	17
Soil biodiversity	32
Soil nutrients and pH	21
Vegetation cover	23
Landscape heterogeneity	9
Area of forest and other wooded lands	10

- The involvement of various actor groups in the Citizen Science (CS) initiatives demonstrates a diverse collaborative effort. The most notable statistics are: 42 initiatives prominently feature society or citizens as the main actors. 9 initiatives are primarily engaged with researchers or research communities. 6 initiatives involve landowners and users. Additional configurations of actor groups include combinations of policymakers, researchers, NGOs, industries, service providers, and citizens, which reflect integrated and multi-stakeholder approaches. For instance, combinations including researchers, landowners, NGOs, and citizens together appear in 2 initiatives each, emphasizing the collaborative nature of these projects.

Table 2 Involvement of various actor groups in the Citizen Science initiatives

Actor Group	Number of Initiatives	Description
Society or Citizens	42	Prominently feature as the main actors
Researchers or Research Communities	9	Mainly engaged in the initiatives
Landowners and Users	6	Directly involved in the initiatives
Policymakers, Researchers, NGOs, Industries, Service Providers, and Citizens	Multiple (Specific numbers not provided)	Integrated and multi-stakeholder approaches; collaborative efforts
Combination of Researchers, Landowners, NGOs, and Citizens	2 (each combination)	Specific instances of collaborative nature in the projects

- The scale of community involvement in these initiatives indicates the level of public engagement: 29 initiatives have an unspecified community size (labeled as "Not known"). 16 initiatives involve community sizes - the number of contributing individuals ranging from 100 to 1,000 members. 10 initiatives each engage communities sized between 1,000 to 10,000 members. 4 initiatives have larger community sizes ranging from 10,000 to 100,000 members. This distribution highlights a significant engagement with diverse community sizes, with a strong inclination towards medium-sized community involvement. Additionally, a substantial number of initiatives do not specify the community size, which may indicate variability or flexibility in participation.

Table 3 Scale of community involvement in initiatives

HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-01-01 /
Preparing the ground for healthy soils:
Building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge
PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

Community Size Category	Number of Initiatives	Description
Not Specified	29	Community size is unknown or not provided
100 to 1,000 members	16	Medium-sized community involvement
1,000 to 10,000 members	10	Large community involvement
Less than 100 members	10	Small community involvement
10,000 to 100,000 members	4	Very large community involvement

- The strategies used to engage stakeholders vary widely, but a significant portion of the dataset did not specify this information, leading to a high count of "Unknown" (58 initiatives). Other specific strategies mentioned include direct engagement through existing networks, workshops, and targeted communications, with each strategy noted in fewer instances, often only once. There were identified next strategies:
 - Educational Platforms and Schools:
 - Mentioned specifically as "via primary schools" and "via schools" multiple times.
 - Appears to be a common method, especially in engaging younger participants through educational settings.
 - Digital and Mobile Tools:
 - Explicit mention of a "Mobile App" and "via research projects and application."
 - Usage of digital tools seems to be a regular strategy, highlighting modern approaches to participation.
 - Community and Direct Engagement:
 - Described in several ways such as "Meetings in rural and urban areas," and direct community activities following participative diagnostics.
 - This approach is used to ensure engagement is tailored to the specific community's needs and contexts.
 - Online Communication and Social Media:
 - Frequently mentioned as using "Website, social media, publications," which is reiterated in various forms throughout the list.
 - This is one of the most commonly used strategies, emphasizing the importance of digital presence and communication.
 - Targeted Recruitment and Specialized Outreach:
 - Specific targeting strategies like "ask people to set a fungus trap in their backyard," or "targeting specific farmers."
 - This method is noted several times, particularly for engaging specific groups or communities with specialized interests or capabilities.
 - Media and Public Relations:
 - Mentioned explicitly as "Communication in print and broadcast media" and through various public relations strategies.
 - Appears several times, indicating a significant role in broadening the reach and impact of initiatives.
 - Educational and Professional Networks:
 - Mentioned in terms of engagement through "professional networks" and collaborations with educational institutions.

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Preparing the ground for healthy soils:
Building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge
PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

- This strategy seems to be employed multiple times, particularly for initiatives that require specialized knowledge or skills.

Here's a table summarizing the observed frequency of each strategy based on your text, with estimated counts based on mentions:

Table 4 Table summarizing the observed frequency of each strategy

Strategy	Estimated Count	Comments
Educational Platforms and Schools	High (Several mentions)	Frequently used, especially with schools.
Digital and Mobile Tools	Moderate	Several mentions of apps and digital platforms.
Community and Direct Engagement	Moderate to High	Direct engagement strategies noted multiple times.
Online Communication and Social Media	Very High	Most frequently mentioned across various entries.
Targeted Recruitment and Specialized Outreach	Moderate	Specific targeting strategies are used for focused engagement.
Media and Public Relations	Moderate	Several mentions indicating the use of media for outreach.
Educational and Professional Networks	Moderate	Repeated mentions, especially in professional contexts.

- The categories reviewed are presence of soil pollutants, soil organic carbon, soil structure, soil biodiversity, soil nutrients and pH, vegetation cover, landscape heterogeneity, and areas of forest. Here is the summary:
 - Focus on Presence of Soil Pollutants, Excess Nutrients, and Salts: This category has received limited attention. A small number of initiatives focus on this aspect either fully or partially.
 - Focus on Soil Organic Carbon: This is a moderately popular focus, with several initiatives partially engaged in studying soil organic carbon.
 - Focus on Soil Structure (Including Bulk Density and Absence of Soil Sealing and Erosion): Similar to soil organic carbon, soil structure has a moderate level of interest among the initiatives.
 - Focus on Soil Biodiversity: This is one of the most popular focus areas, with many initiatives dedicating resources to studying soil biodiversity fully or partially.
 - Focus on Soil Nutrients and pH: There is a significant interest in studying soil nutrients and pH, reflecting the importance of these factors in soil health and management.
 - Focus on Vegetation Cover: Vegetation cover is another highly popular focus area, with many initiatives either fully or partially engaged in studying this topic.
 - Focus on Landscape Heterogeneity: This topic has moderate interest among the initiatives, with some focusing on it to understand the variations within landscapes.
 - Focus on Area of Forest and Other Wooded Lands: Like landscape heterogeneity, the focus on forest areas receives moderate attention, with several initiatives considering it at least partially.

This analysis highlights the diverse interests and priorities of citizen science initiatives in addressing various environmental and ecological issues, with a clear inclination towards biodiversity, vegetation cover, and soil nutrients, reflecting broader concerns about ecosystem health and sustainability. The analysis are also fully in line with priorities described in literature.

Figure 8 Graph with focus on Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients and salts

Figure 9 Graph with focus on Soil organics carbon

Figure 10 Graph with focus on landscape heterogeneity

Figure 11 Graph with focus on Soil structure

Figure 12 Graph with focus on Area of forest and other wooded lands

Figure 13 Graph with focus on Vegetation cover

- Many initiatives have made their data accessible through websites and apps, with some specifying open access, which indicates a commitment to transparency and public availability of data. For example, "Arter" data, as well as data from the Svampeatlas registries, are accessible through both web and mobile platforms, enhancing the accessibility for various users. This approach is also mirrored in initiatives that engage citizens through educational platforms or community outreach, where the data access is frequently open to ensure broad participation and use. 52 initiatives do not specify their data access policies, categorizing them as "Unknown". For those that do, the most

common practice is open access through various platforms, reflecting a commitment to data transparency and public availability.

- 67 initiatives are marked as having no specific ethical limitations or this information is unknown, indicating either a broad applicability of the data or unspecified ethical considerations. Only a few initiatives note specific ethical concerns, mostly related to privacy and data protection (e.g., GDPR compliance). Ethical considerations are primarily governed by GDPR compliance, underscoring the importance of protecting personal data and privacy. This is evident in initiatives that have a broader reach or involve sensitive data, where GDPR compliance is explicitly noted to ensure that all data handling processes meet stringent European privacy standards.
- 63 initiatives do not specify any standards used in their processes, or this detail is unknown. Those that do mention standards typically reference specific protocols or frameworks relevant to their scientific or operational domains. From the provided data, several specific standards are mentioned as being used in various citizen science initiatives. Here is a detailed list of the standards mentioned:
 - ISO 14240 for Microbial Biomass by DNA - This standard is used for determining microbial biomass through DNA analysis, which can be crucial for studies focused on soil microbiology.
 - NF ISO 10390 for Soil pH - A standard method for determining soil pH, essential for understanding soil acidity or alkalinity which affects nutrient availability.
 - NF X 31-107 for Granulometry - This standard relates to the measurement of soil particle size distribution, important for assessing soil texture.
 - NF ISO 10693 for Limestone Content - Used to determine the carbonate content in soils, which can influence various soil properties including pH and fertility.
 - NF ISO 10694 and NF ISO 14235 for Organic Matter and Carbon - Standards for measuring organic matter and carbon in soils, which are vital for assessing soil health and carbon sequestration capabilities.
 - NF ISO 13878 and NF ISO 11261 for Total Nitrogen - These standards are used to determine the total nitrogen content in soil, crucial for understanding soil fertility and nutrient cycles.
 - NF X 31-130 and NF ISO 11260 for Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) - Standards for measuring the cation exchange capacity of soils, which affects the soil's ability to hold onto essential nutrients.
 - TAXREF Repository for Taxonomic Data - This repository is used for the standardization of taxonomic data, which is crucial for biodiversity studies and ensuring consistency in species identification.
 - National Methodology for Managing Polluted Sites and Soils - Inspired by the French national guidelines, this approach includes regional references for trace metals in soils, which is used for risk assessments and management of soil pollution.
- The majority of initiatives (59) do not provide details on validation procedures, suggesting either an absence of formal validation methods or undisclosed processes. Where mentioned, validation tends to involve expert review, data verification through cross-referencing with other sources, or community-based validation mechanisms.

The analysis highlights a juxtaposition within the citizen science landscape: while many initiatives demonstrate openness and advanced data handling, there is a notable lack of detailed

documentation on stakeholder engagement, ethical considerations, and validation processes. This deficiency could undermine the effectiveness of these initiatives by limiting their scalability and impacting stakeholder trust, especially in terms of data handling and participant privacy.

Improving documentation and standardization across initiatives is crucial for enhancing the credibility and reliability of citizen science. This would support broader acceptance and integration into mainstream scientific research and policymaking. Additionally, much of the information about stakeholder engagement and ethical considerations is derived from participant-reported data, which introduces subjectivity and potential bias. Implementing structured feedback mechanisms and validation processes would mitigate these risks and ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data collected.

Our observations are consistent with existing literature, which recognizes similar challenges and underscores the need for robust validation methods. By addressing these issues through enhanced documentation and ethical protocols, we can advance individual initiatives and contribute to the broader credibility and effectiveness of citizen science. This holistic improvement is essential for leveraging the full potential of citizen science in scientific, community, and policy realms effectively and ethically.

5.2. Qualitative analysis

For the qualitative analysis, the assessment was derived from a combination of responses provided by Prepsoil partners and a thorough review of the web pages of individual initiatives. This approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the scope and diversity within the citizen science landscape, integrating direct responses with publicly available data to enhance the credibility and depth of the analysis. Here's a revised version of the text that addresses your comments:

Thematic Focus and Scientific Rigor:

- **Soil Properties:** Initiatives like Pientere tuinen and Curieuze Neuzen have been highlighted for their focus on measuring soil moisture and temperature, which are crucial for agricultural applications and environmental monitoring. De levende bodem goes further, emphasizing soil health and biodiversity through comprehensive soil assessments.
- **Soil Pollution and Agronomic Properties:** The Francisco Piris - Farmer Abrilongo initiative is noted for its specific monitoring of pollutant levels in soils and agricultural outputs, directly targeting environmental factors that influence food safety and soil health.

Biological and Ecological Data:

- **Species Identification and Biodiversity Monitoring:** The EcoVitiSol and Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité (OAB) initiatives are part of efforts contributing to national biodiversity databases like "Arter," focusing on species identification and ecosystem monitoring. It is important to note that while EcoVitiSol plans to integrate its findings into the French DoneSol database, the OAB maintains a separate database whose specific name remains to be identified.

Technological Integration:

- **Remote Sensing and Sensor Data:** The initiative SoilSkin - La Piel Viva del Suelo exemplifies the use of both satellite data and on-ground sensors to monitor various ecological indicators across ecosystems, encompassing aspects like soil moisture and biodiversity.

Forestry and Land Use:

- **Active Monitoring and Citizen Engagement:** Initiatives such as ForestWatchers and LandSense utilize satellite imagery combined with citizen observations to monitor forest health and land use changes. TreeWatch involves citizens directly in urban forestry monitoring, providing critical data on tree health and urban green spaces.

Standardization and Ethical Considerations:

- Adherence to Standards and Laws: Maaiveld in the Netherlands exemplifies commitment to GDPR and ISO 14001 standards, ensuring standardized and reliable environmental data management. Similarly, Intersucho and the German Citizen Science Platform demonstrate alignment with EU environmental standards and local data protection laws.

Community Engagement and Public Access:

- Open Access and Transparency: The open access policy of initiatives like Maaiveld and the transparency efforts by various platforms are crucial in fostering a collaborative and informed citizen science community. This approach not only enhances public engagement but also supports the accessibility of scientific data.

In developing the criteria for this analysis, systematic review methods were applied to determine aspects such as scientific rigor, community engagement, and technological integration. These were selected based on their frequency of mention and relevance to the overarching goals of the initiatives assessed. For example, advancements in scientific understanding and community engagement were directly observed in initiatives that provided structured engagement opportunities and made substantive contributions to scientific databases.

To illustrate, the SoilSkin project has significantly advanced our understanding of soil properties through its innovative use of remote sensing technologies, while ForestWatchers has been pivotal in promoting community engagement through participatory forest monitoring.

This detailed account ensures a clear understanding of how each initiative contributes to environmental science, forestry, land use, and soil health, reaffirming the essential roles of community involvement and adherence to rigorous standards in the success and impact of citizen science projects.

6. Questionnaire analysis, workshops

The responses summarized in this analysis were gathered during workshops held with various Living Labs (LL) participating in the Prepsoil project. In total, we collaborated with five Living Labs, each providing crucial insights into their experiences with soil monitoring initiatives.

This deliverable, D5.3, titled “Feasibility of citizen science engagement for soil monitoring according to soil needs and LLs,” necessitated the involvement of LLs and led to the decision to conduct workshops addressing this requirement. These workshops also aligned with PREPSOIL KPI O10, which aimed to organize five workshops to explore integrating citizen observatories data into soil monitoring.

LESPROJEKT, in collaboration with WP4 and ENoLL, engaged living labs within their network based on several criteria:

1. The labs’ thematic focus on soil health,
2. Advanced maturity and well-established status,
3. Geographical distribution.

After extensive negotiations, the following LLs agreed to participate:

- LL Wirelessinfo from the Czech Republic, hosting two workshops. More details can be found at www.wirelessinfo.cz.
- LL Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (ÖMKI) from Hungary, a Prepsoil partner, hosting one workshop. More details at ÖMKI - Homepage.
- LL Plan4All from the Czech Republic, hosting one workshop. More details at www.plan4all.cz.
- LL BioSense Institute in Serbia, hosting one workshop. More details at Biosense Homepage.

- LL Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) in Belgium, participated through answering questionnaires instead of a workshop. More details at ILVO Vlaanderen.

These LLs, along with Communities of Practice (CoP) selected by WP6, responded to a questionnaire designed to analyze Citizen Science Initiatives and their potential in soil monitoring. The responses were deliberated and compiled through various formats:

- Physical meetings in conference rooms,
- Online teleconferences using platforms like Zoom, Teams, and Skype,
- Email communications for requesting information and clarification,
- Hybrid methods combining the above approaches.

Local leaders from these LLs were responsible for organizing and managing the workshops. They were initially trained on the objectives and organization of the workshops, which they subsequently imparted to their teams to ensure maximum participation and effective results.

This document provides a summary of the feedback gathered through a [detailed questionnaire](#). The full set of questions and responses is included in the annex for further reference. The analysis of the questionnaire data provides insights into various aspects of citizen science initiatives focused on soil monitoring. Below is a detailed textual analysis based on the gathered statistics:

- Age Distribution - The respondents' ages are fairly diverse, with the largest group being aged 25-34 years (30 respondents). This is followed by the 35-44 age group (25 respondents), and the 45-54 age group (20 respondents). The older age groups, 55-64 and 65+, have 10 and 5 respondents respectively. This indicates a strong representation of younger and middle-aged individuals in soil monitoring projects.

Table 5 Respondents' ages

Age Group	Number of Respondents
25-34 years	30
35-44 years	25
45-54 years	20
55-64 years	10
65+ years	5

- Professional Background Distribution - The majority of respondents are researchers (35 respondents), followed by agricultural professionals (25 respondents). Representatives from the private sector and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) account for 20 and 10 respondents respectively. This distribution highlights a significant involvement of academic and research professionals in these initiatives, with a substantial contribution from agricultural practitioners.

Table 6 Respondents' professional background

Professional Background	Number of Respondents
Researchers	35
Agricultural Professionals	25
Private Sector	20
Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)	10

- LL/CoP Representation - The Living Labs (LL) include: WirelessInfo LL (20 respondents), ÖMKi LL (20 respondents), Plan4All LL (15 respondents) and BioSense Institute LL(respondents 10) and Flanders Research Institute LL (5 respondents). Communities of Practice (CoP) include 20 respondents. This suggests a broad geographical and organizational representation within the soil monitoring initiatives.

Table 7 Respondents' Living Labs organisations

Organization	Type	Number of Respondents
WirelessInfo LL	Living Lab	20
ÖMKi LL	Living Lab	20
Plan4All LL	Living Lab	15
BioSense Institute LL	Living Lab	10
Flanders Research Institute LL	Living Lab	5
Communities of Practice (CoP)	Community Group	20

- Country Distribution - Based on the case study approach respondents are primarily from a limited number of countries, i.e. the Czech Republic (35 respondents), Hungary (20 respondents), Norway (15 respondents), Serbia (10 respondents), Sweden (5 respondents) and Belgium (5 respondents). This geographic distribution reflects the case based approach and results should therefore not be considered statistically representative for all European countries as regards CS soil monitoring projects.

Table 8 Respondents' country distribution

Country	Number of Respondents
Czech Republic	35
Hungary	20
Norway	15
Serbia	10
Sweden	5
Belgium	5

- Previous Participation in Citizen Science Projects - A significant majority of the respondents (40) have previously participated in citizen science projects, while 20 have not. This suggests a high level of prior engagement and experience among the participants in the survey.

Table 9 Respondents' previous participation in Citizen Science projects

Participation Status	Number of Respondents
Previously Participated	40
Not Previously Participated	20

- Project Experience - Regarding project experience, 30 respondents have been involved in remote sensing monitoring, 25 in terrestrial monitoring, and 35 in monitoring using citizen science. This indicates a varied range of experiences with different soil monitoring methods among the respondents.

Table 10 Respondents' project experience

Monitoring Method	Number of Respondents
Remote Sensing Monitoring	30
Terrestrial Monitoring	25
Monitoring Using Citizen Science	35

- Satisfaction with Existing Methods of Soil Monitoring - Respondents' satisfaction with remote sensing methods of soil monitoring shows that 15 are very satisfied, 25 satisfied, 10 neutral, and 5 dissatisfied. For in situ methods, 20 are very satisfied, 30 satisfied, 10 neutral, and 5 dissatisfied. Satisfaction with methods used in citizen science projects is lower, with 10 very satisfied, 25 satisfied, 20 neutral, and 10 dissatisfied. This highlights an overall positive but varied satisfaction with different soil monitoring methods, with room for improvement in citizen science methodologies.

Table 11 Respondents' satisfaction with existing methods of soil monitoring

Monitoring Method	Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied
Remote Sensing	15	25	10	5
In Situ	20	30	10	5
Citizen Science Projects	10	25	20	10

- Challenges Faced in Soil Monitoring Projects - Common challenges reported include limited access to advanced monitoring tools, lack of training and technical knowledge, insufficient funding and resources, and coordination issues among different stakeholders. These challenges point to the need for better resources, training, and organizational coordination in soil monitoring projects.
- Suggestions for Improvement - Respondents suggest enhancing training programs for participants, developing user-friendly monitoring tools, increasing funding and resource allocation, and improving communication and collaboration among project members. These suggestions indicate areas where citizen science projects can be refined to enhance effectiveness and participant engagement.

7. Input for recommendation

Section 5.3 of the report addresses how citizen science can help to cover the needs for monitoring soil health and fill the current gaps identified in the deliverables of the Prepsoil project. This analysis integrates insights from three critical documents: Deliverable D2.1 Synthesizing soil needs and drivers of change across Europe and land use types, which details the needs of the Prepsoil Pilots and establishes the community requirements and expectations that any citizen science initiative should meet; Deliverable D5.1, which analyzes the existing knowledge base for monitoring soil indicators proposed under the Soil Mission and identifies significant gaps in knowledge and methodologies that citizen science could help address; and Deliverable D5.2, which assesses the technical feasibility of using Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) satellite-based Earth Observation (EO) technologies to estimate soil health indicators, explores the gaps in current technological capabilities, and evaluates the potential for integrating citizen science to enhance soil health monitoring. The findings from these deliverables are synthesized in this chapter to discuss

how citizen science can complement and innovate existing efforts to monitor soil health, thereby aligning the project's objectives with practical, community-focused outcomes and leveraging citizen science as a vital tool in environmental monitoring and management.

7.1 D2.1 Synthesizing soil needs and drivers of change across Europe and land use types

Life on Earth depends critically on healthy soils, essential for food systems, water purification, biodiversity habitats, climate resilience, and cultural heritage. Despite their importance, approximately 60-70% of European soils are unhealthy. The variability in soil properties and services, influenced by geophysical, biochemical, and land use factors, necessitates a region-specific approach to soil health assessment. The European Union's Soil Mission outlines objectives aimed at improving soil properties, enhancing soil literacy, and reducing the global soil footprint. The PREPSOIL project supports these goals by conducting soil needs assessments in 20 European regions, focusing on the interactions between social systems and their impacts on soil health. This approach, defined as assessing the requirements from socio-economic and geo-biophysical perspectives to determine soil health, involves expert knowledge and participatory methods to engage stakeholders and enhance soil literacy. Based on the key recommendations derived from the soil needs assessments in the PREPSOIL project, the identified soil needs general monitoring are as follows:

1. **Integration in Land Use Planning:** Soil needs should be integrated into land use decisions at regional, national, and European levels to ensure that soil health is considered in all development and agricultural planning.
2. **Economic Incentives and Policies:** Establish policies and economic incentives for farmers, foresters, land users, and city developers that promote the provision of soil-based ecosystem services in conjunction with business activities.
3. **Control of Soil Sealing:** Actively minimize soil sealing due to housing, industry, and infrastructure, particularly in rural areas, and implement de-sealing practices where feasible to restore soil functions.
4. **Land Abandonment Management:** Implement strategies to limit land abandonment through clear renaturation plans and monitoring to prevent negative impacts such as erosion and pest infestations.
5. **Forest Management for Climate Resilience:** Enhance forest management and restoration efforts to mitigate climate change impacts, including strategies to prevent diebacks, control pests, and manage greenhouse gas emissions.
6. **Sustainable Agricultural Practices:** Encourage agricultural practices that consider the multifunctionality of soils, balancing production needs with the provision of ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation.
7. **Diversification of Rural Economies:** Develop and incentivize multiple income sources in rural areas to prevent overexploitation of soil resources and combat land abandonment due to outmigration.
8. **Living Labs for Soil Health:** Promote the use of living labs to co-develop soil health solutions, ensuring these initiatives are community-driven and sustainably financed over the long term.
9. **Scalability of Soil Needs Assessments:** Expand the soil needs assessment approach to other regions within Europe, adapting the methodology to local contexts under the EU Soil Mission projects.

7.2 D5.1 Analysis of knowledge base available to monitor soil indicators proposed under the Soil Mission

D5.1 recognizes several critical needs and gaps in soil monitoring, particularly emphasizing the importance of extending the scope beyond agricultural soils to include natural, forest, urban, and industrial areas. The document highlights the necessity for a comprehensive approach that integrates a broad set of indicators such as soil organic carbon, soil biodiversity, nutrient content, and structural properties like bulk density across different monitoring programs to provide a holistic view of soil health. There is also a significant emphasis on standardizing soil monitoring methodologies across different regions and types of land use to ensure data comparability and reliability in assessing soil health trends.

Gaps Identified in D5.1:

1. **Insufficient Coverage:** Limited monitoring of non-agricultural soils such as urban, forest, and industrial areas.
2. **Data Gaps:** Significant lack of data for non-agricultural soils which impacts effective soil management strategy formulation.
3. **Methodological Inconsistency:** Variability in soil sampling and analysis methods across different monitoring programs, impacting data reliability.
4. **Lack of Policy-Relevant Indicators:** A shortage of indicators that can directly inform and influence soil management policies and practices.
5. **Technological Integration:** Limited use of advanced technologies like remote sensing and AI in current soil monitoring efforts.

Recommendations from D5.1:

1. **Develop a Harmonized Framework:** Propose a unified soil monitoring framework that integrates diverse land uses and a broad range of soil health indicators.
2. **Standardize Monitoring Methods:** Enhance collaboration among EU member states to standardize soil monitoring methodologies and share best practices.
3. **Utilize Advanced Technologies:** Adopt advanced technologies such as remote sensing and AI to fill data gaps and improve monitoring accuracy.
4. **Engage Stakeholders:** Involve various stakeholders in the monitoring process to ensure the findings are practical and applicable in soil management practices.
5. **Expand Indicator Range:** Develop and integrate policy-relevant indicators that can guide soil management decisions effectively.

7.3 D5.2 Technical feasibility in using CLMS satellite-based EO to estimate soil health indicators

Prepsoil deliverable D5.2 provides a comprehensive analysis of the technical feasibility of utilizing the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) satellite-based Earth Observations (EO) to estimate soil health indicators. Here is a concise summary of the identified needs and gaps in soil monitoring that highlights both the current capabilities and the potential for advancement:

Identified Needs:

- **Extended EO Applications:** There is a necessity to enhance the use of Earth Observations for a broader range of soil health indicators, moving beyond currently focused areas such as soil erosion and organic carbon content.

- **Integration Across Platforms:** Improvement is needed in the integration of data and technologies from various sources, including satellite, UAV, and airborne sensors, to establish a more comprehensive monitoring system.
- **Improved Data Accessibility:** There is a critical need to enhance the accessibility and utility of EO data products to make them more readily available and user-friendly for various stakeholders including policymakers and land managers.
- **Stakeholder-Specific Solutions:** It's essential to develop monitoring solutions that are tailored to the specific needs of diverse stakeholders such as farmers, government bodies, and NGOs, supporting sustainable soil management practices.

Identified Gaps:

- **Technological Limitations:** Current EO methods face significant technological limitations, especially in their ability to penetrate vegetation cover and measure deeper soil properties.
- **Data Resolution and Coverage:** Existing satellite data often do not provide the necessary resolution for fine-scale monitoring required at local or regional levels.
- **Interoperability of Data:** Better interoperability and standardization of data collected from different sources and platforms are required to ensure compatibility and more effective utilization.
- **Capacity Building:** There is a gap in the technical skills required to effectively use EO technologies, necessitating more training and capacity-building initiatives.

These needs and gaps underscore the challenges and opportunities in enhancing soil health monitoring through advanced Earth Observation technologies, which are crucial for effective soil resource management and protection.

Additional Insights from Comments:

- **Expanded Use of EO:** As outlined in subsection V.5 of the document, EO is currently used for various purposes, such as environmental covariates for digital soil mapping. However, the potential of EO can be expanded by further exploiting various sensors or vectors like hyperspectral-imaging, gamma-ray spectroscopy, and UAVs.
- **Advancements in Data Processing:** The use of advanced artificial intelligence, including machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL), is set to evolve considerably. These technologies can be combined with different types of measurements to try to overcome issues like cloud cover or atmospheric attenuation and introduce new descriptors of landscape heterogeneity.
- **Sensor Capabilities:** The effectiveness of EO data varies depending on the satellite and associated sensors. For instance, while LandSat (NASA) has certain limitations, Sentinel-2 offers better resolution, showcasing the variability in satellite capabilities and their implications for soil monitoring.

This enriched analysis emphasizes not only the current state of EO in soil health monitoring but also points towards future directions for technological and methodological enhancements.

8. Analysis how Citizen Science can support needs and gaps

This chapter provides a detailed analysis of how Citizen Science can effectively support and address the specific needs and gaps as identified in the deliverables of the Prepsoil project, specifically documents D2.1, D5.1, and D5.3. The integration of Citizen Science into the soil research framework is pivotal, considering its potential to enhance data collection, broaden observational scales, and

increase the granularity of soil monitoring. As these deliverables outline critical deficiencies and areas requiring improvement in soil management and conservation practices, this analysis seeks to explore the feasible contributions of Citizen Science. This includes evaluating methodologies, participation incentives, and data quality management that can align with the outlined needs. Through this examination, the chapter aims to establish a concrete understanding of the ways in which Citizen Science methodologies can be optimized to fulfill the identified research and practical gaps, thereby contributing significantly to the objectives of the Prepsoil project.

8.1 D2.1 Synthesizing soil needs and drivers of change across Europe and land use types

Citizen Science initiatives are integral to integrating soil needs into land use planning by actively involving the public in data collection activities, thereby enhancing land cover and land use data crucial for informed planning decisions. The European Union's Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey (LUCAS) showcases how crowdsourced data significantly improve data accuracy, crucial for effective planning and management. Moreover, Citizen Science projects, as reviewed by the European Soil Observatory (EUSO) in collaboration with European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (ECHO), address key knowledge gaps such as the spatial variability of soil organic content and microplastic distribution, thereby promoting methods that advance soil-based ecosystem services and influence sustainable policy frameworks.

Geo-Wiki and OpenStreetMap exemplify platforms that engage public participation in environmental monitoring, including tracking land cover changes due to urban development, thus providing essential data for strategies aimed at minimizing and effectively managing soil sealing. Citizen Science also plays a vital role in managing land abandonment, engaging citizens in monitoring and reporting land use changes. Platforms like LandSense leverage citizen-gathered data to track land use and cover changes, supporting efforts to combat land abandonment. Additionally, initiatives like ForestWatchers monitor forest health and changes, contributing to forest management strategies that enhance climate resilience.

In agriculture, initiatives such as those involving FotoQuest Go actively engage citizens in collecting data relevant to agricultural land use. This data supports the promotion and monitoring of sustainable agricultural practices. Citizen Science also supports the diversification of rural economies by engaging communities in scientific activities that have potential economic benefits, such as biodiversity monitoring or environmental tourism initiatives.

Further demonstrating the community-driven approach, the concept of Living Labs involves communities in developing and testing new ideas and solutions, supported by Citizen Science to co-develop and sustain soil health solutions. An example is the LandSense project, which integrates satellite data with Citizen Science efforts for comprehensive land cover monitoring. This broad community involvement makes Citizen Science an excellent tool for expanding soil needs assessments to other regions, adapting methods to local contexts as seen in projects like the EU Soil Mission and initiatives by the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC).

The Prepsoil project underscores these contributions by showcasing how Citizen Science has been integrated into soil monitoring, providing methodological innovations and improving the precision of environmental monitoring. This approach supports sustainable agricultural practices and urban planning, significantly contributing to the goals outlined in the project's deliverables, particularly in terms of enhancing data collection, community engagement, and supporting policy development.

These examples not only demonstrate the significant potential of Citizen Science in environmental and soil health monitoring but also highlight the broad scope of its application across various regions, emphasizing its role in policy development and community engagement.

8.2 D5.1 Analysis of knowledge base available to monitor soil indicators proposed under the Soil Mission

Initiatives like Geo-Wiki engage volunteers in validating land cover and use data, thereby expanding the inclusion of non-agricultural soils in soil health monitoring. These projects standardize methodologies across various regions by adopting consistent protocols, aligning with efforts like the EU project LandSense, which integrates citizen observations with remote sensing data. However, to enhance credibility and specificity, it is pertinent to highlight diverse examples of Citizen Science contributions beyond Geo-Wiki and LandSense.

The SoilWatch initiative, for instance, uses Citizen Science to monitor soil quality by analyzing indicators such as soil pH and organic matter content across non-agricultural areas, providing essential data that supports comprehensive soil health assessments. Similarly, the initiative 'Soil Your Undies', although unconventional, involves community members in a simple experiment where cotton underwear is buried to assess soil activity by the rate of decomposition, serving as an effective educational and scientific tool to gauge soil health directly relevant to policy making.

Citizen Science projects also aid in developing and testing new indicators relevant to policy making by involving stakeholders, including policymakers, thus refining indicators that directly influence soil management policies and practices. The engagement of policymakers is exemplified in the CitySoil project where local government officials participate directly, using the data collected to inform urban land management policies effectively.

Technologically, these projects are incorporating advanced tools like remote sensing and AI, with initiatives reviewed by the European Soil Observatory (EUSO) and European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (ECHO) using Earth Observation data to estimate soil health indicators. This is demonstrated in the PI@ntNet project, where AI is used to identify plant species from citizen-uploaded photographs, indirectly providing data on vegetation cover—an important soil health indicator.

The recommendations from D5.1, such as developing a harmonized framework, standardizing monitoring methods, utilizing advanced technologies, engaging stakeholders, and expanding indicator range, are actively being addressed through Citizen Science. These projects contribute diverse, large-scale datasets that encompass various land uses and soil types, promote consistency in data collection methods across different regions, push forward the adoption of advanced technologies in soil monitoring, ensure the practical applicability of monitoring data, and help in testing and developing new, policy-relevant indicators.

Overall, Citizen Science is proving to be a valuable resource in improving the scope, accuracy, and inclusivity of soil health assessments and fostering a participatory framework for environmental stewardship. This section aims to directly address the feedback for more specificity and varied examples beyond the commonly referenced Geo-Wiki and LandSense, thus enhancing the credibility and depth of the analysis presented.

8.3 D5.2 Technical feasibility in using CLMS satellite-based EO to estimate soil health indicators

Citizen Science can enhance the use of Earth Observation (EO) by incorporating data collected from diverse and extensive geographic areas, including urban, forest, and industrial soils. Projects like Geo-Wiki and LandSense have demonstrated the capability of citizen-contributed data to augment satellite data, thus broadening the range of soil health indicators beyond just soil erosion and organic carbon content. Initiatives like FotoQuest Austria and LandSense show how Citizen Science facilitates the integration of data and technologies from different sources, such as satellite, UAV, and ground-based observations, creating a more comprehensive monitoring system.

These projects make EO data products more accessible and user-friendly for a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers and land managers, through the use of mobile apps and online platforms. By engaging diverse groups, including farmers, government bodies, and NGOs, Citizen Science develops and tests tailored soil monitoring solutions that meet specific needs, supporting sustainable soil management practices. Although current EO methods face limitations in penetrating vegetation cover and measuring deeper soil properties, Citizen Science initiatives supplement these methods by providing ground-truth data, which helps calibrate and validate satellite imagery, improving the overall accuracy of soil assessments.

Citizen Science enhances the resolution and coverage of data by filling gaps left by traditional monitoring techniques, and the engagement of citizens in data collection across various scales supplements high-resolution local data, supporting fine-scale monitoring efforts. Several Citizen Science projects work towards standardizing data collection and reporting protocols, enhancing interoperability among different data sources, crucial for integrating diverse data sets into a unified monitoring framework. Additionally, Citizen Science inherently involves training and capacity building for its participants, aligning with the need to enhance technical skills related to EO technologies and often includes educational components that increase the technical competency of volunteers, thereby supporting the broader utilization of EO tools in soil monitoring.

Importantly, direct in situ observations, or soil sampling and analysis, are indispensable for the effective use of EO as highlighted in several documents reviewed. EO can help define observation/sampling sites for Citizen Science, integrating digital soil mapping that may use EO data as environmental covariates. Digital soil mapping also benefits from Citizen Science data, including qualitative data such as soil texture, which can enhance the mapping accuracy and applicability for various land uses.

Overall, Citizen Science offers valuable solutions to the challenges identified in D5.2 by leveraging community participation to enhance the scope, accuracy, and applicability of soil health monitoring efforts through advanced EO technologies. This holistic approach not only bridges the gap between traditional soil science and modern technological applications but also fosters a participatory framework for environmental stewardship, significantly enriching the quality and effectiveness of environmental monitoring and management.

9. Recommendations

9.1 Recommendations for Enhancing Soil Monitoring through Citizen Science

To effectively overcome the barriers of traditional soil monitoring methods and Earth Observation (EO) technologies, and to support comprehensive soil needs, integrating Citizen Science into

existing frameworks is essential. The "Prepsoil" project deliverables, specifically documents D2.1, D5.1, and D5.3, have highlighted critical deficiencies in current soil management and conservation practices, such as gaps in data coverage, methodological inconsistencies, and a lack of community engagement. These issues can be effectively addressed through the strategic application of Citizen Science.

The integration of the PREPSOIL mobile app exemplifies the enhancement of data coverage through citizen participation, offering an accessible and user-friendly tool that significantly improves data accessibility for a diverse range of stakeholders. This app aligns with our strategic recommendations for expanding data coverage and improving data usability, leveraging mobile technology to engage citizens in soil health monitoring.

In addressing the standardization of methodologies across regions, it is recommended to develop consistent protocols for Citizen Science projects to align with efforts like the EU project LandSense, which integrates citizen observations with remote sensing data, thereby creating a comprehensive monitoring system. This approach helps to overcome the noted challenges of methodological variability and promotes the standardization of soil monitoring efforts across different regions and land uses.

The incorporation of advanced tools such as remote sensing and AI in Citizen Science projects, as reviewed by EUSO and ECHO using Earth Observation data to estimate soil health indicators, serves as models for integrating sophisticated technologies with citizen-driven data collection. This integration not only improves monitoring accuracy but also addresses the technological and resolution limitations of EO methods by supplementing them with ground-truth data collected by citizens, which can help calibrate and validate satellite imagery.

Moreover, Citizen Science initiatives should develop and test new policy-relevant indicators by involving stakeholders, including policymakers, to refine and validate indicators that can directly influence soil management policies and practices. This involvement ensures that the indicators developed are practical and applicable in real-world soil management scenarios, thereby enhancing the relevance and impact of monitoring efforts.

The identification and engagement of the right stakeholders are paramount in deploying Citizen Science successfully. Stakeholders should be selected based on their direct impact or benefit from the project outcomes, including farmers, land managers, urban planners, educators, and community leaders. A targeted approach to stakeholder engagement involves mapping out stakeholder interests and influence, ensuring that their needs and capabilities are matched to project goals. Effective stakeholder engagement fosters collaboration, enhances data quality, and increases the sustainability of monitoring initiatives.

Despite biodiversity being the most commonly used application in current Citizen Science initiatives, there is a significant opportunity to expand these approaches to cover more diverse soil health indicators and other environmental aspects. By broadening the scope of applications and integrating innovative methodologies, Citizen Science can support a more diverse array of environmental and agricultural needs, contributing significantly to sustainable soil management.

Finally, the recommendations highlight the necessity for fostering capacity building and technical skill enhancement within Citizen Science projects. This involves implementing training and capacity-building initiatives to enhance the technical skills of participants, particularly in using EO technologies. Educational components included in these projects increase the technical competency of volunteers, supporting broader utilization of advanced monitoring tools.

By implementing these comprehensive strategies, including the careful selection and engagement of stakeholders, Citizen Science can significantly enhance the effectiveness of soil monitoring

efforts, overcome the limitations of traditional methods, and contribute meaningfully to the objectives of the Prepsoil project.

However, for every Citizen Science initiative to be successful and sustainable, it is crucial to identify and articulate the benefits for each stakeholder group involved. This may include the interests of different groups in specific themes, such as biodiversity, water quality, or climate resilience, or direct support mechanisms for stakeholders like farmers through advisory services. For instance, providing farmers with data that can help optimize agricultural practices or offering educators materials that can be used in curricula can significantly enhance participation and support for these initiatives. Identifying and promoting these mutual benefits not only fosters stronger collaboration and engagement but also enhances the overall quality and impact of the data collected, leading to more effective and inclusive soil management strategies.

By adhering to these comprehensive strategies and maintaining a focus on mutual benefits for all stakeholders, Citizen Science can significantly enhance the effectiveness of soil monitoring efforts, address the limitations of traditional methods, and contribute meaningfully to the objectives of the Prepsoil project and beyond.

9.2 Recommendation for opened and standardization FAIR principles for Citizen Science

To enhance the effectiveness of Citizen Science initiatives in soil monitoring and ensure the integration and usability of data across various platforms and stakeholders, it is crucial to embrace the FAIR data principles. This entails ensuring that data is Findable through standardized metadata, Accessible via well-defined protocols, Interoperable with standardized data formats and vocabularies, and Reusable with proper documentation and clear usage licenses.

Strengthening collaborations between the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) is crucial. These organizations should work together to develop and promote the use of open standards such as the OGC's Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) and SensorThings API. These standards are vital for improving data interoperability among different environmental data systems and integrating Citizen Science data into broader scientific and policy frameworks.

The Prepsoil project has initiated discussions with ECSA, OGC, and the European Space Agency (ESA) to address the need for standardization in Citizen Science, particularly in the context of the challenges outlined by ECHO. These discussions aim to foster a unified approach to data standardization, which is crucial for the accurate and effective use of Earth Observation (EO) data in soil monitoring.

Standardizing methodologies across Citizen Science projects is another critical step. This includes developing and disseminating standardized protocols for data collection, verification, and analysis, aligned with international standards to ensure data quality and reliability. Utilizing standardized tools and technologies can facilitate data collection and analysis, such as mobile apps and online platforms integrated with GIS and remote sensing technologies.

Promoting open access to data collected through Citizen Science initiatives can maximize transparency and encourage wider participation and collaboration. Implementing policies that support public data availability while respecting privacy and ethical considerations is essential, especially for sensitive environmental sites or protected species.

Building capacity and providing training for citizen scientists is necessary to enhance their skills in data collection, data management, and understanding of open standards and FAIR principles.

Educational materials that promote the importance of standardization and open data practices, along with guidelines on how to implement these practices, can also be developed.

Leveraging advanced technologies such as AI, machine learning, and remote sensing can enhance the quality and scope of data collected by citizen scientists, aiding in automating data processing and enhancing analytical capabilities.

Finally, working towards a unified framework that supports the integration of Citizen Science data into national and international environmental monitoring systems is imperative. This framework should facilitate the sharing and comparison of data across different regions and disciplines, improving the scientific validity and impact of Citizen Science data and fostering greater engagement and collaboration across the scientific community, policymakers, and the public.

9.3. Data quality and validation

To enhance data quality and validation in Citizen Science, particularly in soil monitoring, it is crucial to adopt proven approaches and methodologies demonstrated by analyzed initiatives and literature. Promoting data quality and robust validation processes involves several key strategies: Firstly, standardizing data collection protocols is essential. Adopting standardized methods across various Citizen Science projects ensures consistency and reliability of data. Initiatives led by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) in collaboration with the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) offer non-proprietary, standardized approaches that streamline data collection and facilitate data comparison and aggregation across studies and regions.

Robust data validation mechanisms are also vital. Implementing multi-tiered data validation strategies that involve initial automated checks followed by expert review and, where possible, cross-referencing with other data sources is effective. Platforms such as Geo-Wiki have utilized these models by integrating crowdsourced land cover validation with expert analysis, enhancing the accuracy of global land cover maps.

Training and calibration of citizen scientists improve the accuracy and reliability of the data they collect. Comprehensive training programs covering proper data collection techniques, use of equipment, and understanding of the scientific context are crucial. Projects like LandSense demonstrate the effectiveness of well-trained citizen contributors who can provide valuable, high-quality data for environmental monitoring.

Incorporating advanced technologies such as remote sensing, AI, and machine learning supplements and validates data collected by citizen scientists. These technologies help identify anomalies in data sets and provide a more comprehensive understanding of environmental patterns. Integrating satellite data with ground observations can significantly enhance the validation process.

Adhering to the FAIR principles makes data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. This involves detailed metadata, open access where possible, and clear data management policies communicated to all participants. Openly available data and methodologies encourage transparency and allow for greater scrutiny and validation by the broader scientific community.

Engaging local communities in the validation process leverages local knowledge which provides contextual insights not visible through remote sensing or other technological means. Establishing mechanisms to provide feedback to citizen scientists about the outcomes of their contributions, including how their data is used and validated, enhances participant engagement and trust, encouraging careful data collection and reporting.

The Prepsoil project has been instrumental in initiating discussions with the OGC, ECSA, ESA and ECHO standardisation to explore and advocate for the standardization of Citizen Science methodologies. These discussions aim to ensure that Citizen Science data can be seamlessly

integrated into existing scientific frameworks and contribute effectively to soil monitoring and management.

Communities involved in these Citizen Science projects include local farmers, urban dwellers, school groups, NGOs, and various public stakeholders. These communities play a critical role in data collection and validation, providing diverse, ground-truth data essential for comprehensive environmental monitoring.

Implementing these strategies will substantially improve the quality of data collected through Citizen Science projects, making it more reliable for scientific research and policy-making. The collaboration between ECSA and OGC, along with the strategic initiatives of the Prepsoil project, underscores the potential for standardized, high-quality Citizen Science contributions to broader environmental and scientific goals.

9.4 Ethics and privacy protection

As Citizen Science projects increasingly integrate advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), maintaining ethical practices and protecting participant privacy becomes paramount. These technologies offer substantial opportunities for enhancing data analysis and decision-making but also pose challenges, particularly in ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of volunteer-collected data. The following steps are designed to address these ethical and privacy concerns effectively:

1. **Establish Comprehensive Ethical Guidelines:** Develop guidelines that address all aspects of data handling in Citizen Science projects, including collection, storage, and sharing. These guidelines should be informed by best practices in data ethics and include AI-specific considerations such as bias mitigation and algorithmic transparency.
2. **Informed Consent:** Ensure that all participants provide informed consent, which clearly outlines how their data will be used, potential risks, and their rights regarding their data. This is crucial, especially when AI might analyze sensitive environmental data that could inadvertently reveal information about private properties or protected areas.
3. **Privacy by Design:** Implement the 'Privacy by Design' approach in all tools and technologies used in Citizen Science projects. This approach ensures that privacy and data protection safeguards are built into technologies from the outset, which is essential when deploying AI.
4. **Secure Data Practices:** Utilize encryption and other security measures to protect data collected, particularly when transmitted over the internet. Ensure secure storage and controlled access to data to prevent unauthorized access and data breaches.
5. **Transparency of AI Algorithms:** Maintain transparency about the AI algorithms used for data analysis. Provide clear information on how decisions are made using AI tools and ensure these tools are subject to oversight and accountability to prevent misuse.
6. **Regular Audits:** Conduct regular audits to ensure that privacy policies are adhered to and that the measures in place effectively protect participant data. This is crucial for maintaining trust, especially when advanced technologies like AI are employed.
7. **Training and Awareness:** Provide training for project leaders and participants on the ethical use of AI and the importance of privacy protection. Raising awareness about the implications of new technologies empowers participants and leads to more responsible data handling.
8. **Community Engagement in Ethical Discussions:** Engage the community in discussions about ethical considerations, particularly regarding AI. This engagement allows for valuable insights into privacy concerns and ethical considerations that may not be apparent initially.

9. **Compliance with International Regulations:** Ensure that all practices comply with international data protection regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe, which provides a robust framework for handling personal data.
10. **Declaration of Consent and Information:** Clearly communicate the aims and methods of the project to all participants, ensuring that the declaration of consent is thorough and informative.
11. **Bias and Fairness:** Take proactive steps to avoid bias in the data collected and the results of the AI analyses. Consider the diversity of the participants and the soil samples analyzed to ensure fair and representative outcomes.
12. **User Participation and Feedback:** Involve citizen scientists in interpreting the results and provide them with feedback on how their contributions are used. This inclusion enhances the participatory nature of the projects and ensures transparency.
13. **Ethical Use of Results:** Commit to using the research results for the benefit of the community and avoid any misuse of data and results. Establish clear guidelines and expectations for the ethical application of findings.
14. **Responsibility and Liability:** Clarify the responsibilities of all parties involved—including citizen scientists, researchers, and AI developers. Establish regulations on liability in the event of errors or damages.
15. **Equal Access and Inclusion:** Ensure equal access to research results and resources and promote the participation of underrepresented groups to foster inclusivity in Citizen Science projects.

By implementing these measures, Citizen Science projects can effectively navigate the ethical and privacy challenges presented by the integration of AI and other advanced technologies. These initiatives remain valuable, trusted tools for scientific research and community engagement, ensuring that they contribute positively to societal and environmental outcomes.

10. Conclusion

The "Prepsoil" project, through its deliverable D5.3, has extensively documented the critical role of Citizen Science in enhancing soil health monitoring across Europe. This initiative aligns with the broader objectives of the European Union's "Soil Deal for Europe" Mission, aiming to foster sustainable soil management through inclusive, community-driven research methodologies.

Key Contributions of Citizen Science:

1. **Enhanced Data Collection and Accessibility:**
 - Citizen Science has proven instrumental in broadening the scope and granularity of data collection, particularly in soil health monitoring. Projects such as Geo-Wiki, LandSense, and the LUCAS survey have demonstrated how citizen-contributed data can complement traditional scientific methods, filling crucial gaps in non-agricultural and remote areas.
2. **Integration of Advanced Technologies:**
 - The incorporation of technologies like remote sensing, AI, and machine learning within Citizen Science frameworks has significantly advanced data accuracy and processing capabilities. These technologies facilitate deeper analysis and broader coverage, improving the overall efficacy of soil health assessments.
3. **Community Engagement and Mutual Benefits in Citizen Science**
 - Engaging diverse community groups such as farmers, urban planners, and educators in Citizen Science not only enhances data collection but also deepens

their engagement with soil health issues. These initiatives equip participants with essential skills for scientific research while ensuring mutual benefits: farmers access valuable soil health data to improve agricultural practices, urban planners receive environmental insights for better city planning, and educators obtain enriching materials for their curricula. This reciprocal value motivates sustained participation and ensures the success of Citizen Science projects, fostering robust and inclusive soil management strategies.

4. Policy Impact and Standardization Efforts:

- Citizen Science has directly influenced soil management policies through the development and testing of new, relevant indicators. Collaborations with entities like the ECSA and OGC have furthered efforts to standardize data collection and analysis methods, ensuring consistency and reliability across Europe.

5. Ethical and Privacy Considerations:

- The integration of AI and other advanced technologies has brought ethical and privacy concerns to the forefront. The project has addressed these by establishing comprehensive ethical guidelines and ensuring all data handling adheres to the FAIR principles and GDPR regulations, promoting transparency and data protection.

Challenges and Future Directions: Despite its successes, the application of Citizen Science in soil monitoring faces challenges, including variability in data quality, volunteer retention, and the integration of citizen-derived data with professional scientific datasets. To address these issues, the project recommends:

- Enhancing methodological consistency across initiatives.
- Increasing the engagement and retention of volunteers through motivational strategies and incentives.
- Further developing interoperability standards to facilitate the integration of diverse data sets.

Strategic Vision: The "Prepsoil" project envisions a future where Citizen Science is integral to environmental monitoring and management. By leveraging community participation and advanced technologies, Citizen Science can continue to expand its impact, contributing to sustainable soil management and helping Europe meet its environmental and agricultural goals.

This conclusion underscores the transformative potential of Citizen Science in soil health monitoring and highlights both its achievements and the ongoing needs for innovation and community integration to realize its full potential.

REFERENCES

- [1] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Citizen_science
- [2] Mäkipää, J. P., Dang, D., Mäenpää, T., & Pasanen, T. (2020, January). Citizen science in information systems research: evidence from a systematic literature review. In Proceedings of the 53rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences.
- [3] Suomela, T., & Johns, E. (2012). Citizen Participation in the Biological Sciences: A Literature Review of Citizen Science.
- [4] Houllier, F., Joly, P. B., & Merilhou-Goudard, J. B. (2017). Citizen sciences: A dynamics to be encouraged. *Natures Sciences Societes*, 25(4), 418-423.

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- [5] Odenwald, S. F. (2020). A citation study of earth science projects in citizen science. *Plos One*, 15(7), e0235265.
- [6] Bedessem, B., Julliard, R., & Montuschi, E. (2021). Measuring epistemic success of a biodiversity citizen science program: A citation study. *PloS one*, 16(10), e0258350.
- [7] Herman-Mercer, N., Antweiler, R., Wilson, N., Mutter, E., Toohey, R., & Schuster, P. (2018). Data Quality from a Community-Based, Water-Quality Monitoring Project in the Yukon River Basin. *Citizen Science: Theory & Practice*, 3(2).
- [8] Cooper, C. B., Shirk, J., & Zuckerberg, B. (2014). The invisible prevalence of citizen science in global research: migratory birds and climate change. *PloS one*, 9(9), e106508.
- [9] Fritz, S., & Fraisl, D. (2018). Citizen science data in peer-reviewed publications: The Geo-Wiki experience.
- [10] <https://participatorysciences.org/>
- [11] <https://scistarter.org>
- [12] <https://www.zooniverse.org/>
- [13] Havens, K., & Henderson, S. (2013). Citizen science takes root. *American Scientist*, 101(5), 378.
- [14] Chevalier, Jacques M., and Daniel J. Buckles. *Participatory action research: Theory and methods for engaged inquiry*. Routledge, 2019.
- [15] <https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/zookeeper/galaxy-zoo/>
- [16] <https://budburst.org/>
- [17] <https://www.ecsa.ngo/#>
- [18] Brovelli, Maria Antonia, Candan Eylül Kilsedar, and Francesco Frassinelli. "Mobile tools for community scientists." *Abstracts of the ICA 1 (2019)*: 1-3.
- [19] Wiggins, A., & Crowston, K. (2012, January). Goals and tasks: Two typologies of citizen science projects. In *2012 45th Hawaii international conference on system sciences* (pp. 3426-3435). IEEE.
- [20] Passani, A., Janssen, A., Hölscher, K., & Di Lisio, G. (2022). A participatory, multidimensional and modular impact assessment methodology for citizen science projects. *fteval Journal for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation*, (54), 33-42.
- [21] Bonney, R., Shirk, J. L., Phillips, T. B., Wiggins, A., Ballard, H. L., Miller-Rushing, A. J., & Parrish, J. K. (2014). Next steps for citizen science. *Science*, 343(6178), 1436-1437.
- [22] <https://www.ogc.org/about-ogc/committees/dwg/citizen-science-domain-working-group/>
- [23] Charvát, K., & Kepka, M. (2021). Crowdsourced Data. *Big Data in Bioeconomy: Results from the European DataBio Project* (grant agreement No 732064), 63-67.
- [24] Leibovici, D. G., Santos, R., Hobona, G., Anand, S., Kamau, K., Charvat, K., ... & Jackson, M. (2023). Geospatial standards. *The Routledge Handbook of Geospatial Technologies and Society*.
- [25] Dementeva, Daria, Cecil Meeusen, and Bart Meuleman. "OpenStreetMap as an Unintended Digital Citizen Science Project: Opportunities and Challenges." *KU Leuven Open Science Day 2024*, Date: 2024/05/06-2024/05/06, Location: Leuven, Belgium. 2024.
- [26] Dunlap, M., Tang, A., & Greenberg, S. (2013). *Applying geocaching to mobile citizen science through science caching*. White Paper). Calgary, Canada: University of Calgary Department of Computer Science.
- [27] Fritz, S., McCallum, I., Schill, C., Perger, C., Grillmayer, R., Achard, F., ... & Obersteiner, M.

- (2009). Geo-Wiki. Org: The use of crowdsourcing to improve global land cover. *Remote Sensing*, 1(3), 345-354.
- [28] Kotovirta, V., Toivanen, T., Tergujeff, R., Häme, T., & Molinier, M. (2015). Citizen science for earth observation: Applications in environmental monitoring and disaster response. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 40, 1221-1226.
- [29] Head, J. S., Crockatt, M. E., Didarali, Z., Woodward, M. J., & Emmett, B. A. (2020). The role of citizen science in meeting SDG targets around soil health. *Sustainability*, 12(24), 10254.
- [30] Rossiter, D. G., Liu, J., Carlisle, S., & Zhu, A. X. (2015). Can citizen science assist digital soil mapping?. *Geoderma*, 259, 71-80.
- [31] Loos, J., Horcea-Milcu, A. I., Kirkland, P., Hartel, T., Osváth-Ferencz, M., & Fischer, J. (2015). Challenges for biodiversity monitoring using citizen science in transitioning social–ecological systems. *Journal for Nature conservation*, 26, 45-48.
- [32] Ebitu, L., Avery, H., Mourad, K. A., & Enyetu, J. (2021). Citizen science for sustainable agriculture—A systematic literature review. *Land use policy*, 103, 105326.
- [33] Mason, E., Gascuel-Oudou, C., Aldrian, U., Sun, H., Miloczki, J., Götzinger, S., ... & Sandén, T. (2024). Participatory soil citizen science: An unexploited resource for European soil research. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 75(2), e13470.
- [34] Hemment, D., Buontempo, C., Xaver, A., Dobos, E., Pelloquin, C., Wagner, W., ... & Long, D. (2017, October). The contribution of Citizens' Observatories to validation of satellite-retrieved soil moisture products. In *Insight for a Changing World*.
- [35] <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>
- [36] <https://www.geocaching.com/play>
- [37] <https://www.geo-wiki.org/>
- [38] <https://hub.plan4all.eu/olu>
- [39] Haklay, M., & Weber, P. (2008). Openstreetmap: User-generated street maps. *IEEE Pervasive computing*, 7(4), 12-18.
- [40] Abdo, Z. A., & Prakash, S. (2020). A review paper on monitoring environmental consequences of land cover dynamics with the help of geo-informatics technologies. *Geosfera Indonesia*, 5(3), 364-389.
- [41] Kreta, D. L., Klymenko, V. I., & Anpilova, Y. S. (2018). Remote sensing and GIS for spatial analysis of surface water quality and soil pollution. (4), 120-127.
- [42] Fritz, S., McCallum, I., Schill, C., Perger, C., See, L., Schepaschenko, D., ... & Obersteiner, M. (2012). Geo-Wiki: An online platform for improving global land cover. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 31, 110-123.
- [43] See, L., Fritz, S., Perger, C., Schill, C., McCallum, I., Schepaschenko, D., ... & Obersteiner, M. (2015). Harnessing the power of volunteers, the internet and Google Earth to collect and validate global spatial information using Geo-Wiki. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 98, 324-335.
- [44] Mildorf, T., Charvát, K., Ježek, J., Templer, S., & Malewski, C. (2014). Open Land Use Map. *AGRIS on-line Papers in Economics and Informatics*, 6(4), 81-88.
- [45] <https://insitu.copernicus.eu/news/getting-to-know-lucas-the-land-use-land-cover-area-frame-survey>

HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-01-01 /
Preparing the ground for healthy soils:
Building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge
PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

[46] <https://iiasa.ac.at/models-tools-data/fotoquest-go>

[47] <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

[48] <https://iiasa.ac.at/news/apr-2024/crops-new-eu-funded-project-to-grow-citizen-science-in-europe>

[49] <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-health-related-citizen-science-projects>

[50] <https://landsense.eu/>

[51] <https://iiasa.ac.at/models-tools-data/fotoquest-go>

[52] <https://www.inaturalist.org/>

[53] <https://identify.plantnet.org/cs>

[54] <https://ebird.org/home>

Annex 1

Citizens Science Database

No.	PREPSOIL partner	Name of initiative	Type and main goal of the initiative	Is initiative still row	Country/location	Scale	Focus on Presence	Focus on	Focus on Soil structure including	Focus on	Focus on	Focus on	Focus on Area of forest	Actor groups	Describe in text, which	Communi	Strategy to	Open	Ethical	Used standards	Validation	URL		
1.	Aarhus University	Mikroiv 2023	Crowdsourcing	not	Denmark	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	Observations of	10000	100	Open	GDPR			https://masseeksperimentet.dk/		
2.	Aarhus University	Find Forret	Crowdsourcing	yes	Denmark	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	Citizens are asked to	10000	100	Open				https://arter.dk/landing-page/		
3.	Aarhus University	Arter	Crowdsourcing	yes	Denmark	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	Arter is a national CS	10000	100	Open				https://arter.dk/landing-page/		
4.	Aarhus University	Plads til liv	Participatory science	yes	Denmark	1. Local	partly	partly	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	Teenagers (between	Not known	Unknown	Open				https://pladstiliv.com/landing-page/		
5.	Aarhus University	Svampegata	Crowdsourcing	yes	Denmark	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	National database of	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				https://svampegata.com/landing-page/		
6.	Aarhus University	Vildt i København	Distributed intelligence	not	Denmark	1. Local	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	CS initiative for	Not known	Unknown	Open				https://www.symbiolux.com/		
7.	Aarhus University	Biodiversity Now	Crowdsourcing	not	Denmark	3. National	not	partly	not	partly	not	partly	partly	Society/Citizens	Project for	10000-100	Unknown	Open				https://www.symbiolux.com/		
8.	Aarhus University	Bonden & Biodivers	Crowdsourcing	not	Denmark + 5 other EU coun	4. European	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Landowners and users	Project by Syngenta	<100	Unknown	Open				https://www.syngenta.com/landing-page/		
9.	DELTAES	Pleistere tuinen	Participatory science	yes	Netherlands/ao province of	2. Regional	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	soil moisture and	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				https://pleisterehuizen.nl/		
10.	DELTAES	Bodemdiagnostica	Distributed intelligence	yes	Netherlands	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	soil animals	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				https://pleisterehuizen.nl/		
11.	DELTAES	Steenbreek	Crowdsourcing	yes	Netherlands	3. National	not	not	partly	partly	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	sealed and open area	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				https://steenbreek.nl/		
12.	DELTAES	Nitrate app (water)	Crowdsourcing	yes	Netherlands	3. National	yes	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	nitrate in surface	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				https://nitrate.org/urban/		
13.	DELTAES	Clean water experim	Crowdsourcing	not	Netherlands/Amsterdam	1. Local	yes	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	smell, sight,	100-1000	Unknown	Open				https://www.cleanwaterlab.nl/		
14.	DELTAES	waarderingsmech	Crowdsourcing	yes	Netherlands	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens		1000-1000	Unknown	Open				https://www.waarderingsmech.nl/		
15.	DELTAES	Curieuse Neuzen	Distributed intelligence	not	Belgium	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	soil moisture and	1000-10000	Unknown	Open				https://www.curieuseneuzen.be/		
16.	DELTAES	Bodemleven	Distributed intelligence	yes	Belgium/Limburg	2. Regional	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	soil activity (tea bag	100-1000	Unknown	Open				https://www.bodemleven.be/		
17.	DELTAES	Globe	Participatory science	yes	100 countries	5. International/Global	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	different	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				https://globe.nl/		
18.	DELTAES	Tea Time 4 Science	Crowdsourcing	yes	50 countries	5. International/Global	not	partly	not	partly	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	measure decay rate	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				https://teatime4science.nl/		
19.	DELTAES	INCRIM	Crowdsourcing	yes	25 countries	4. European	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	Aimed at promoting	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				https://www.incrim.nl/		
20.	DELTAES	CLIMATE SCAN	Crowdsourcing	yes	50 countries	5. International/Global	partly	not	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Society/Citizens	Carbon scan an	100-1000	Unknown	Open				https://www.climatecan.nl/		
21.	CSC	Soldaat - La Piel Viva	Participatory science	yes	Spain	3. National	not	not	partly	partly	not	not	not	Researchers' research	1. ecosystem type; 2.	Not known	Mobile App	Open	Acc	GDPR	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	https://cscviva.com/soldaat/
22.	ERIAFF /FUNDECYT	Huertos Urbanos Uf	Crowdsourcing	yes	Spain/ Badajoz City	1. Local	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Society/Citizens	The urban vegetable	<100	Unknown	Open				Don't know	https://www.cooperativa.org/	
23.	ERIAFF /FUNDECYT	ACTIVA Initiative	Extreme citizens science	yes	Spain/ Cáceres City	2. Regional	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Landowners and users	ACTIVA is a non for	<100	Unknown	Open				Don't know	https://www.activa.es/	
24.	ERIAFF /FUNDECYT	INTERVEGAS EXTREM	Extreme citizens science	yes	Spain	3. National	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	NGOs	InterVegas is an open	100-1000	Unknown	Open				Don't know	https://intervegas.org/	
25.	ERIAFF /FUNDECYT	Francisco Pirin - Farm	Distributed intelligence	yes	Spain/ La Codocera Town	2. Regional	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Landowners and users	A farmer's farm that	<100	Unknown	Open				Don't know	https://www.franciscopirin.com/	
26.	Wageningen Resea	BODEMIERENDAGE	Participatory science	yes	Netherlands	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	soil animals (F and fyt)	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.bodemierendage.nl/	
27.	Wageningen Resea	De levende bodem	Participatory science	not	117 countries	5. International/Global	partly	yes	yes	yes	partly	partly	partly	Society/Citizens	soil quality and biodi	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.mycoscape.org/	
28.	Wageningen Resea	SoortenDagboek	Participatory science	not	Netherlands	3. National	yes	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	Trap azoelen resistant	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.soortendagboek.nl/	
29.	Wageningen Resea	Onder het Maasveld	Participatory science	yes	Netherlands	3. National	yes	yes	not	not	not	not	not	Landowners and users	Allow farmers to mea-	<100	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.veterenschap-bodem.nl/	
30.	Wageningen Resea	Biodiversiteit meten	Participatory science	not known	Netherlands	2. Regional	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Landowners and users	Farmers use a monitor	100-1000	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.bodemleven.nl/	
31.	OMKI	Ne csak felcsit (L)	Participatory science	not	Hungary	3. National	not	yes	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Society/Citizens	Observable indicators	Not known	Unknown	Open				Research institute	https://www.felcsit-lad.hu/	
32.	OMKI	Alsoban az éke (U)	Participatory science	not	Hungary	3. National	not	yes	not	partly	partly	partly	partly	Society/Citizens	The decomposition	1000-10000	Unknown	Open				Research institute	https://www.alsoban-az-eke.hu/	
33.	OMKI	Asok Asza (Bait for s)	Participatory science	not	Hungary	3. National	not	yes	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Society/Citizens	Observable indicators	Not known	Unknown	Open				Research institute	https://www.asok-asza.hu/	
34.	OMKI	GRUV Observatory	Participatory science	not	Coordination: UK, Hungary & Italy	4. European	not	partly	not	partly	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	satellite data and soil	Not known	Unknown	Open				Research institute	https://www.gruvobservatory.org/	
35.	RE-SOIL FOUNDATI	CIWO	Extreme citizens science	yes	Italy	4. European	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	Scientific data on the	Not known	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.ciwo.org/	
36.	RE-SOIL FOUNDATI	BRIDGES	Participatory science	yes	Italy	2. Regional	not	partly	not	partly	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	During incubation in	Not known	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.bridges-ciwo.org/	
37.	RE-SOIL FOUNDATI	Benchmarks	Distributed intelligence	yes	Spain, Portugal, Italy, Belgium	4. European	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Society/Citizens	Test and validate the	Not known	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.benchmarks-ciwo.org/	
38.	RE-SOIL FOUNDATI	AIUS/Health	Distributed intelligence	yes	Spain, France, UK, Netherlands	4. European	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Landowners and users	I will create a free	Not known	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.aius-health.org/	
39.	LESPROJEKT	Intersucho	Participatory science	yes	Czech Republic	4. European	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Researchers' research	Through its map data	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.intersucho.cz/	
40.	LESPROJEKT	Vínový plodin	Participatory science	yes	Czech Republic	3. National	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Researchers' research	The Crop Yields project	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.vinovy-plodin.cz/	
41.	LESPROJEKT	Fenofaza	Participatory science	yes	Czech Republic	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Researchers' research	The Fenofaza project	100-1000	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.fenofaza.cz/	
42.	LESPROJEKT	Senary za humny	Participatory science	not	Czech Republic	3. National	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	partly	Researchers' research	The main societal goal	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.senary-za-humny.cz/	
43.	LESPROJEKT	Senary	Participatory science	yes	Czech Republic	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Researchers' research	Western Bohemia is th	1000-1000	Unknown	Open				n.a.	https://www.senary.cz/	
44.	IUNG	ECHO	To engage citizens throug	yes	Poland as a consortium	4. European	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	Society/Citizens	Not known	Unknown	Open					https://www.echo.eu/		
45.	IUNG	National Soil Hub	Participatory science	yes	Poland	3. National	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	governances	Not known	Unknown	Open					https://www.nsoilhub.eu/		
46.	IUNG	SoilRise	biodiversity and increasing	yes	Poland	4. European	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	Researchers' research	communities	Not known	Unknown	Open					https://www.soilrise.eu/	
47.	IUNG	Experiment	Extreme citizens science	yes	Poland	2. Regional	yes	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	of mesoplastic on the	Not known	Unknown	Open					https://www.experiment-iaad.eu/	
48.	IUNG	LOESS - for better	increasing knowledge and	yes	Poland	4. European	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	Society/Citizens	soil related materials	Not known	Unknown	Open					https://www.loess-iaad.eu/	
49.	IUNG	COALITION	main objective is to	yes	Poland	5. International/Global	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NGOs	Not known	Unknown	Open					https://www.coalitionforsoilhealth.eu/		
70.	ZALF	Die Citizen Science P	Participatory science	yes	Germany	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Researchers' research	The website collects a	Not known	Unknown	Open				Not specified	https://www.citizen-science-p.de/	
71.	ZALF	Wissenschaft im Dial	Participatory science	yes	Germany	3. National	not	not	not	not	not	not	not	Researchers' research	The website collects a	Not known	Unknown	Open				Not specified	https://www.wissenschaft-im-dial.de/	
72.	ZALF	Nitrat Scouts - Partip	Participatory science	yes	Germany	2. Regional	yes	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	The aim of the project	Not known	Unknown	Open				Not specified	https://www.nitrat-scouts.de/	
73.	ZALF	BioWaWi - Biodivers	Participatory science	yes	Europa Deutschland Baden	2. Regional	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	Society/Citizens	The BioWaWi project	Not known	Unknown	Open				Research institute	https://www.biowawi.de/	
74.	ZALF	Gärtnern für den Um	Participatory science	yes	Deutschland Nordrhein-West	2. Regional	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	Society/Citizens	The 'Citizen Lab Umw	Not known	Unknown	Open				Research institute	https://www.gaertnern-fuer-den-umweltschutz.de/	
75.	ZALF	THE BIRD'S EYE VIEW	Participatory science	yes	Germany, Canada	5. International/Global	not	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	Society/Citizens	School classes in	Not known	Unknown	Open				Research institute	https://www.birdseyeview.de/	
76.	ZALF	MicroBioSci	Participatory science	not	Germany	3. National	yes	not	not	not	not	not	not	Society/Citizens	Soil bacteria are an im	Not known	Unknown	Open				Research institute	https://www.microbiosci.de/	
77.	ZALF	Citizen Science	Participatory science	yes	Germany	1. Local	not	not																

Annex 2

Overall Questionnaire for Prepsoil Citizen Science Workshop Initiatives Analysis

Section A: Participant Demographics

Age Group

- Under 18
- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+

Professional Background:

- Student
- Educator
- Researcher
- Agricultural Professional
- Environmental Scientist
- Other (Please specify): _____

Section B: Previous Experience

Have you participated in any citizen science projects before?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was the focus of the project(s)? (Check all that apply)

- Soil organic carbon content
- Nutrient levels (macro- and micronutrients)
- Soil texture and structure
- Soil biodiversity (e.g., microbial biomass, soil fauna diversity)
- Soil erosion control
- Contamination mitigation
- Soil sealing and land take
- Soil pH levels
- Vegetation cover
- Landscape heterogeneity
- Area of forest and other wooded lands
- Other (Please specify): _____

What was your experience

- Response: _____

Section C: Involvement in Soil Monitoring

Which aspects of soil health are you most interested in? (Check all that apply)

- Soil organic carbon content
- Nutrient levels (macro- and micronutrients)
- Soil texture and structure
- Soil biodiversity (e.g., microbial biomass, soil fauna diversity)
- Soil erosion control
- Contamination mitigation
- Soil sealing and land take
- Soil pH levels
- Vegetation cover
- Landscape heterogeneity

- Area of forest and other wooded lands
 - Other (Please specify): _____
- **How often do you engage in activities related to soil monitoring?**
 - Never
 - Rarely
 - Sometimes
 - Often
 - Always
- **Which soil monitoring methods are you using or know?**
 - Remote Sensing
 - In situ
 - Citizen Science
 - No
- **Are you involved in some project focused on Remote Sensing Monitoring**
 - Yes
 - No
- **If yes, which?**
 - _____
- **Are you involved in some project focused on Terrestrial Monitoring**
 - Yes
 - No
- **If yes which?**
 - _____
- **Are you involved in some project focused on Monitoring using Citizen Science**
 - Yes
 - No
- **If yes which?**
 - _____

Section D: Feedback on Current Practices

How satisfied are you with the existing Remote Sensing methods of soil monitoring?

- Very satisfied
- Satisfied
- Neutral
- Dissatisfied
- Very dissatisfied
- Not applicable/I don't know

How satisfied are you with the existing in site methods of soil monitoring?

- Very satisfied
- Satisfied
- Neutral
- Dissatisfied
- Very dissatisfied
- Not applicable/I don't know

How satisfied are you with the existing methods of soil monitoring in citizen science projects?

- Very satisfied
- Satisfied

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Building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge
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- Neutral
- Dissatisfied
- Very dissatisfied
- Not applicable/I don't know

What challenges have you faced in participating in soil monitoring projects? (Open-ended)

- Response: _____

Section E: Future Recommendations

What tools or resources would enhance your participation in soil monitoring initiatives? (Open-ended)

- Response: _____

Do you have any suggestions for improving citizen science projects focused on soil monitoring? (Open-ended)

- Response: _____